

Pathos

Open Science Impact Pathways

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Validated model of Key OS Impact Pathways and guidelines/recommendations

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
APC	Article Processing Charge
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
DAC	Development Assistance Committee
Diamond OA	Diamond Open Access
DMP	Data Management Plan
EDI	Equity, Diversity, Inclusion
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
Gold OA	Gold Open Access
Green OA	Green Open Access
HAL	Hyper Article en Ligne
Hybrid OA	Hybrid Open Access
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IP	Intellectual Property
KIP	Key Impact Pathways
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OS	Open Science
PathOS	Open Science Impact Pathways (Horizon Europe project)
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
RCAAP	Repositórios Científicos de Acesso Aberto de Portugal
R&D	Research and Development
RiPATHs	Charting Impact Pathways of Investment in Research Infrastructure (Horizon 2020 project)
Published OA	Published Open Access
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SME	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprise
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UniProt	Universal Protein Resource

Executive Summary

The PathOS project on Open Science impact pathways set out to understand and demonstrate how **Open Science**—making research freely available, transparent, and inclusive—can create benefits for academia, society, and the economy.

The project examined across three years three main questions:

1. What impacts does Open Science have?
2. How do those impacts happen?
3. What helps or hinders these impacts?

We found that Open Science practices such as Open Access publishing, Open/FAIR Data, and Citizen Science are already reshaping research and its role in society. Our findings highlight:

- **Academic Benefits:** Open Science speeds up knowledge sharing, reduces duplication, and increases visibility of research through higher citation rates and broader reuse of data and methods. It also encourages collaboration across disciplines. However, benefits are uneven, with under-resourced researchers often left behind.
- **Societal Benefits:** Making knowledge freely available empowers communities, improves health and environmental outcomes, and strengthens trust in science. Citizen Science and other participatory approaches have proven especially effective at connecting research with real-world challenges.
- **Economic Benefits:** Open Science can reduce costs and speed up research production. Free access to data and tools saves money and time for researchers and companies, and in some cases contributes to the development of new products and jobs. Still, the evidence here is patchy, and much of the claimed economic value is hard to prove directly.
- **Access is not enough:** Simply making research open does not guarantee impact. Quality, timing, and resources for both producers and users of knowledge are critical.
- **Equity matters:** Without careful design, Open Science may unintentionally widen gaps, favouring wealthier institutions and countries.
- **Proof is tricky:** While there are strong signals of impact, it is difficult to isolate the effects of openness from other factors such as funding, excellence, or timing.

To strengthen the positive impacts of Open Science, PathOS recommends:

- Expanding **support for open infrastructures** (like repositories and data platforms).
- Ensuring **equitable participation**, so all researchers and communities can benefit, not just the well-funded.
- Focusing on **quality and meaningful access**, so that open outputs are reliable, reusable, and truly usable by diverse groups.

- Investing in better **methods and evidence** to understand, quantify and demonstrate impacts over time.

Open Science has the potential to make research faster, fairer, and more useful for society and the economy. The PathOS project provides evidence-based pathways showing how these impacts occur and offers practical guidance to help policymakers, institutions, and researchers unlock its full value.

1. Introduction

This report presents a synthesis of findings from across the PathOS project to create a coherent vision of evidence-based, Open Science Impact Pathways, that can be operationalised and further tested in academic, economic, and societal contexts. It concludes with recommendations for how to increase Open Science impact.

1.1. Mechanisms of Open Science that lead to impact

We define Open Science as a diverse coalition of researchers, policymakers, managers and administrators based in academic institutions, funding organisations, disciplinary bodies (scholarly societies) and industry (including publishers). As Field (2022, 190) has noted, Open Science is perhaps best seen as “a constellation of multiple, diverse communities of practice, with shifting, mutable boundaries, in which a collective identity and enterprise is being continually negotiated.” As such, it encompasses various practices, underpinned by multiple values and principles. The 2021 UNESCO definition (UNESCO 2021a) categorises Open Science as involving practices of open scientific knowledge, Open Science infrastructures, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems. These practices are underpinned by values such as quality and integrity, collective benefit, and equity and fairness, as well as a range of principles including transparency, responsibility and collaboration.

This diversity of aims, activities and intended outcomes, along with methodological issues regarding the heavily correlational nature of many studies, makes drawing consistent chains of causality across this picture difficult (Klebel and Traag 2025). Within the tradition of realist evaluation (a theory-led method for social programme evaluation), the principle of generative causality “holds that, to infer a causal outcome (O) between two events (X and Y), one needs to understand the underlying mechanism (M) that connects them and the context (C) in which the relationship occurs” (Pawson et al. 2005, 21–22).

For Open Science, we conceptualise these mechanisms them based on philosopher Helen Longino’s argument that there are three senses in which we can understand “knowledge” (Longino 2001, 80ff.):

- **Content:** Knowledge as “outputs”, i.e., the outcomes of knowledge-productive practices. Content can be represented and stored mentally, bodily or materially (via documents and other media) and can be shared.

- **Process:** Knowledge as “knowledge productive practices”, i.e., the practices whereby inputs like research questions and hypotheses become outputs in the form of scientific content.
- **Agency:** Knowledge as “knowing”, i.e., the interrelation of subject (the knower), representation (content, as described above), and the object or objects of knowledge. Longino understands the knowing subject to be essentially (and formatively) limited by their location in time, space and (scientific) society, who are hence never mere followers of “context-independent and value-neutral methodological rules.” Hence, “the attribution of knowledge in the relational sense must include some acknowledgment of the social (i.e., interdependent) character of the subjects to which knowledge is attributed” (Longino 1990).

Based on these three senses of knowledge, we propose a model of three underlying Open Science mechanisms:

- **Access:** Extension of knowledge as content, i.e., increasing the availability and manipulability of research objects, primarily to enable reuse and boost research impact for collective benefit.
- **Transparency:** Enabling openness of knowledge as process, i.e., increasing knowledge about underlying research practices and decision-making, primarily to boost the accountability, integrity and quality of research.
- **Participation:** Extension of knowledge as agency, i.e., enable new forms of researcher collaboration and inclusion of a diversity of other types of actors (like the public in Citizen Science), primarily to increase equity, diversity and inclusion and thus boost the societal relevance of research.

We understand these mechanisms to correlate to Open Science interventions, like Open Access publishing, data sharing, sharing of other research outputs and processes, and collaboration, as elaborated in Table 1.¹

Table 1. Overview of Open Science mechanisms, activities and intended effects

OS mechanism	OS activities	Intended effects
Increased access to outputs	Making publications Open Access, pre-printing, data-sharing, publishing methods and	<i>Primary aim: Unlock value</i> Actors globally are empowered to reuse research for their own benefit (e.g., researchers can build on each other's work, societal and economic actors can innovate), resulting in higher returns on investment from academic, societal and economic innovation.

¹ For an extended presentation of this model-in-development of Open Science mechanisms, including the history and ideology of the Open Science movement, see Annex A.

	protocols, sharing code/software	
Increased transparency of processes	Sharing of data and code, Open Methods (pre-registration, registered reports, protocol sharing), workflows, Open Peer Review	<i>Primary aim: Increase quality</i> Researchers are incentivised to observe greater research integrity and avoid questionable research practices, checks on reproducibility are enabled, leading to higher research quality. This then leads to greater trust in research amongst researchers and societal actors (promoting reuse) and greater efficiency overall since resources are not wasted trying to build on unreliable research.
Increased participation of diverse actors	Collaboration via digital platforms, participatory research approaches, Citizen Science	<i>Primary aim: Enable equity, diversity and inclusion</i> Researchers globally can work together more effectively, and societal actors are included in research processes, increasing the efficiency and scope of research processes, leading to greater societal relevance and public engagement, and fostering greater equity, diversity, and inclusion overall.

We situate our conceptualisation of these mechanisms of Open Science within the PathOS impact pathway logic (Figure 1). Within PathOS, we understand impact to be “long-lasting, elementary and wide-spread change” that can be “direct or indirect, intended or unintended, [and] relate to behavioural and/or systemic changes” (Dekker et al. 2023). We understand that it is achieved through a series of events that begin with inputs, like funding, skills, or staff, which support Open Science activities (Open Access publishing, sharing Open/FAIR Data, practicing open methods, etc), which lead to immediate outputs (access, transparency and participation), then to outcomes (like reuse of research outputs), and then to impacts (increases in quality, equity, or enhanced innovation, among other things) (Figure 1). Within this impact pathway logic, access, transparency, and participation, as mechanisms of Open Science, are outputs of Open Science practices (activities).

Figure 1. PathOS Open Science impact pathway logic

1.2. The PathOS project

The PathOS project, focused on Open Science Impact Pathways, aimed to collect evidence of impacts driven by Open Science, to identify and study the pathways to impact driven by them, and to identify and study both enabling factors of and barriers to impact. The project examined three types of impact: academic, societal and economic, and considered how the pathways to them may intersect or overlap.

Aiming to develop an evidence-based understanding of such Open Science impact pathways, PathOS was carried out in six stages (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. PathOS project design

In stage 1, we **scoped** and synthesised the published evidence of Open Science impact, looking at academic (Klebel et al. 2025), societal (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024) and economic impacts separately (Tsipouri et al. 2025).

During stage 2 we developed a **conceptual framework for modelling** Open Science impact pathways – an Open Science intervention logic – that we tested and refined throughout the project (Dekker et al. 2023; Karasz et al. 2024).

Next (stage 3), we developed a suite of impact indicators to **quantify** Open Science impact, and provided methods for a wide variety of indicators, published as a living [Open Science Indicator Handbook \(Indicator Handbook\) \(Apartis et al. 2024\)](#).

Both the conceptual framework and the indicators were **operationalized** during stage 4 through six case studies designed to provide causal evidence of Open Science impact (Stravropoulos et al. 2025a). These case studies (Figure 3) focus on infrastructures and practices for sharing open outputs (publications, data, code and software) and investigated impacts within academia, industry, and society. Together, they tested a range of impact indicators and provided evidence-based feedback to the development of the Indicator Handbook and to the development of evidence-based pathways to impact.

Figure 3. Snapshot of PathOS case studies

Then, during stage 5, we carried out two **cost benefit analysis** exercises on two Open Science resources featured in our case studies – UniProt (the Universal Protein Resource), a global, expert-curated protein database widely used in biomedical research, and RCAAP (Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal), a national, multidisciplinary repository consolidating Portuguese research outputs (Catalano et al. 2025a). This exercise provided a different type of evidence to that found in the literature and otherwise established by the case studies, contributing compelling evidence to the economic case for Open Science, as well as establishing broader benefits (to society and academia) of Open Science infrastructures and practices.

Finally, during stage 6, we conducted a **synthesis** of all project findings to validate and revise our conceptual framework, solidify our evidenced-based Open Science impact pathways, and offer recommendations to support greater Open Science impact based on our evidence. This deliverable reports on this latter phase.

1.3. Overview of this report

Chapter 2 provides a comprehensive methodological overview of PathOS's six-stage approach, including case study designs, causality guidance development, stakeholder engagement processes, and tool operationalization methods. Chapters 3–5 present PathOS's integrated findings synthesizing evidence from systematic literature reviews, six empirical case studies, cost-benefit analysis applications, indicator development and testing, and extensive stakeholder consultation across academic (3), societal (4), and economic (5) impact domains. These chapters demonstrate how PathOS's empirical work - from UniProt and RCAAP economic evaluations to COVID-19 artifact reuse analysis to French repository utilization patterns - validates, challenges, and extends the existing evidence base. Chapter 6 synthesizes key findings and methodological insights, while Chapter 7 presents evidence-based recommendations derived from the project's comprehensive research program.

2. Methods

As described in the Introduction chapter, PathOS was carried out in six stages, designed to progressively build evidence-based Open Science impact pathways, with each subsequent stage providing feedback to those prior. This design ensured that all project components and outputs remained synchronized and mutually validated. PathOS advances impact evaluation practice through key innovations: systematic causality identification, AI-driven computational approaches for large-scale analysis, rigorous mixed-methods integration across quantitative and qualitative evidence, a Cost Benefit analysis framework (CBA) adapted for Open Science contexts, and comprehensive testing across diverse contexts from national infrastructures to emergency responses. All developments build on systematic state-of-the-art assessment through comprehensive scoping reviews and indicator compilation. In this chapter, we describe the project approach in greater detail, examining how each stage informed those before and after, while highlighting the key advances that PathOS contributes to impact evaluation practice.

2.1. Stage 1: Scope

The purpose of Stage 1 was to assess the state of the art in impact assessment methodology and evidence of impact driven by Open Science. This stage consisted of three scoping reviews that used a unified methodology, focused on academic, societal, and economic impacts of Open Science. As described in the preregistered protocol (Ross-Hellauer, Klebel, et al. 2022), these reviews were carried out using the PRISMA for Scoping Reviews methodological framework and included academic, snowballing, and grey literature searches focused on impacts derived from Open Access publishing, Open/FAIR data, open methods, open code/software/tools, Citizen Science and open evaluation. The primary research question pursued was, “What evidence exists in the literature regarding the effect of Open Science on (1) academic, (2) societal, and (3) economic impact of research?” Secondary research questions interrogated the presence of both positive and negative, direct, and indirect impacts; the mechanisms that lead to impact, distinguishing between correlation and causation events within the impact pathway; enabling or inhibiting factors; presence of methods of assessment or indicators of impact; trade-offs between different types of impact; and knowledge gaps.

Established academic databases (Scopus and Web of Science) were used for the initial searches for each study, carried out simultaneously. Snowball sampling using the OpenAlex database followed based on literature deemed in scope, as did grey literature searches in sources including EU Publications Office, CORDIS, and the Center for Open Science, among others. Literature published after 1 January 2000 in English was considered in scope; the three reviews ultimately analysed over 400 studies. Additional methodological details can be found in the study protocol (Ross-Hellauer, Klebel, et al. 2022) and in the published papers that report on

academic (Klebel et al. 2025), societal (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024) and economic impacts (Tsipouri et al. 2025).

The results of this stage, reported as part of the synthesised findings presented in Chapters 3–5 in this report (Stage 6), supported the development of Open Science impact indicators (Stage 3) (Apartis et al. 2024), informed the design and execution of the case studies (Stage 4) (Stavropoulos et al. 2025a), and played a significant role in revising and validating the impact pathway model and in the development of key (evidence-based) impact pathways (Stage 6) (Karasz et al. 2024). Additionally, these studies each make a **substantial contribution to the state-of-the-art understanding of Open Science impact**, providing the first systematic, unified methodology synthesis across academic, societal, and economic domains simultaneously, which had never before been systematically studied and synthesised in this way.

2.2. Stage 2: Conceptualise the model

The purpose of Stage 2, carried out simultaneously with Stage 1, was to draft the Open Science intervention logic and develop a conceptual model of Open Science impact pathways to help us formulate the right questions to ask when measuring the impacts. This stage involved both the development of the conceptual framework (Dekker et al. 2023) and of a method to establish causality in impact pathways (Klebel and Traag 2025).

The conceptual framework for PathOS was developed using the Theory of Change approach described in Dekker et al. (2023) and in concert with OECD/DAC criteria for policy evaluation to identify stages in evaluation and impact analysis to create guidance for a framework for key impact pathways. This model was built upon the RiPATHs model and using OECD terminology (inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, impacts). This work included the creation of a framework for determining causal mechanisms and how they work, which can be validated through evidence and expert consultation, and provided baseline definitions of academic, societal and economic impact which were operationalised in the scoping reviews described in Stage 1, and throughout the rest of the project. Additionally, other key vocabularies and taxonomies were defined for the project and the phased approach and feedback loops throughout the project were clarified in greater detail. This work, published as **D1.1 Open Science Intervention Logic** (Dekker et al. 2023), laid out that impact pathways would be identified in three steps throughout the project:

1. Identify impact pathways based on the intervention logic framework and the Theory of Change through literature review and case studies;
2. Define cumulative pathways from specific Open Science interventions; and
3. Zoom in to specific pathways to provide narrative detail.

Building on this conceptual framework, PathOS created the **innovative structural causal models approach** to establishing causality in Open Science impact pathways (Klebel and Traag 2025). This approach responds to the challenge of making sound causal claims when aiming to establish what impact Open Science has on academia, society and economy. Part of this challenge relates to the common saying that correlation does not imply causation: if two events or phenomena co-occur, this does not mean that one is causing the other. Scientific fields have come up with different approaches to solving this puzzle. To inform the field of research on research and lay the foundation for further work in PathOS, we developed a structural causal model approach aimed at equipping researchers within the project and beyond to think more clearly about causation. This conceptual framework provided the foundation for developing sound causal identification strategies, which were then implemented through various empirical methods appropriate to each research context.

We describe the approach in conceptual terms and illustrate it using a hypothetical example that is related to PathOS: how to identify the causal impact of certain scientific practices on citations and reproducibility.

Figure 4. Hypothetical structural causal model on Open Science as presented in Klebel and Traag, 2025

Figure 4 illustrates how different variables (nodes) are causally connected (arrows); for example, how research Novelty and Rigour affect Citations both directly and indirectly through Open data sharing and Data reuse. This visual framework helps researchers distinguish causal relationships from mere correlations when studying Open Science impacts.

The work helped shape our understanding of how to investigate causality across PathOS and was operationalised in both Stages 3 and 4, described below.

2.3. Stage 3: Quantify

The purpose of Stage 3 was to develop metrics (data, methods, tools) to identify the effects of Open Science. This was done with a mix of qualitative and quantitative approaches designed to embed the identification of causal effects within the impact pathway logic. During this stage, metrics were gathered from the literature, and some were operationalised and tested within the PathOS case studies (Stage 4). Findings from the case studies were used to validate and update those indicators deployed within PathOS. This iterative process led to refinement of existing indicators and development of new ones based on practical implementation experiences and operationalization feedback from all case studies. The work of Stage 3 is presented in the PathOS Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook², which covers various indicators measuring aspects around Open Science itself, their academic, societal and economic impacts, and reproducibility (Apartis et al. 2024). The Handbook comprises 31 indicators across these five categories, each composed of multiple metrics, with detailed descriptions, methods, datasets, and limitations. However, not all are equally well-developed, as will be discussed in subsequent chapters.

Because establishing causality within impact pathways is challenging, as described in the introduction to structural causal models above (Klebel and Traag 2025), we cannot provide straightforward *indicators of effects of Open Science* due to the combinatorial number of possible effects. Each effect necessitates careful reasoning about causal inference. To address this challenge, the Handbook begins with a dedicated chapter on causality, providing practical guidance and examples of 'causal indicators' to help readers distinguish correlation from causation. The Handbook then provides guidance on how to operationalise various indicators to facilitate rigorous studies of Open Science effects based on our conceptual framework.

The Handbook includes some indicators that are less well-developed but vital for studying Open Science impact. This reflects our approach: the Handbook serves as both an inventory of current possibilities and a roadmap for future development. This innovative resource was designed by an interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder team through indicator sprints, stakeholder feedback, and validation workshops. As many relevant indicators continue to evolve, the Handbook is presented as a dynamic website (wiki-format) open to ongoing community

² <https://handbook.pathos-project.eu/>

contributions beyond the project lifecycle, serving as a valuable resource for the Open Science community.

2.4. Stage 4: Operationalise

The six PathOS case studies were designed in relation to the state-of-the-art (Stage 1) to apply the conceptual framework and causal model approach for studying Open Science impact (Stage 2) and to test and develop indicators for measuring impact (Stage 3). Each case study aimed to produce code, datasets, and methodological tools for data-driven impact assessment. These reusable resources enable evaluation of results and provide concrete guidance on feasibility for future uptake of methods and indicators by other organizations.

Each case study deployed an integrated mixed-method approach with systematic co-creation at the centre (via focus groups), engaging carefully selected expert stakeholders from across the research and innovation landscape. This approach provided privileged access to high-quality data including server logs, usage statistics, and institutional records typically unavailable for external research, while ensuring stakeholder input informed the development of questions, methods, relevant factors and data sources. Cases also employed innovative methodologies including AI-driven approaches for computational analysis, automated data extraction tools, and novel indicators such as topic persistence and Open Access advantage metrics derived from server log analysis.

The case studies aimed to operationalise indicators across diverse contexts, from national infrastructures serving entire research communities to emergency response scenarios with urgent policy implications. They implemented causal identification strategies moving beyond correlation, using propensity score matching, regression with controls, and counterfactual reasoning. They captured effects often ignored in standard evaluation, including topic persistence over time, cross-sector collaboration patterns, and societal usage beyond academia.

Moreover, in terms of the Open Science instruments studied, the focus was primarily on impacts driven by open outputs, but also by infrastructures and other curated open resources, implemented at institutional and national levels. Cross-cutting (e.g., scientific collaboration, gender, reproducibility) and downstream (e.g., acceleration of innovation, health and environmental) impacts were also examined.

The six case studies (see Figure 3), detailed in subsequent chapters, span diverse methodological approaches and contexts. The **Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence** case study investigates whether Green OA (repository self-archiving) versus Published OA affects the long-term vitality of AI-for-Climat research topics, using propensity

score matching to isolate causal effects. The **Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications** case study examines whether referencing datasets/software created by others and producing reusable artifacts correlates with measurable academic, clinical, and economic impact during the pandemic.

The **ELIXIR's Bioinformatics Resources** case study maps innovation pathways from an Open Research infrastructure to industry engagement and patent activity, demonstrating economic impact assessment approaches for publicly funded resources. The **Portuguese Repository Infrastructure RCAAP** case study evaluates how a national repository infrastructure affects research visibility, academic-industry collaboration, and system-wide efficiency through comparative analysis and cost-benefit assessment. The **French Open Access Infrastructure** case study develops novel approaches to measuring societal uptake through systematic server log analysis of HAL³ and OpenEdition⁴ platforms, revealing usage patterns across economic sectors and geographical regions. The **Effects of Data Repositories on Data Usage** case study investigates how repository choice affects subsequent data reuse, focusing on Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) contexts through automated mention extraction, researcher interviews, and citation analysis.

The findings from these case studies are integrated within our synthesis of academic, societal and economic impacts, presented in Chapters 3–5. For more information about the PathOS case studies, see Annex B and Stavropoulos et al. 2025a, 2025b.

2.5. Stage 5: Analyse

During Stage 5 PathOS conducted a cost benefit analysis targeting specific Open Science practices from two case studies, capturing all key elements of the input-output-impact story. PathOS developed an **innovative, mixed-methods, stakeholder validated cost-benefit analysis (CBA) framework specifically designed for Open Science** practices and tested it on two specific practices. The approach developed by PathOS is innovative in that applied established CBA principles and approaches developed for analysing investments in science and research, including research infrastructures, to analyse the costs and benefits of Open Science practices.

As described in PathOS Deliverable 4.2 (Delugas et al. 2025), CBA is an analytical tool to assess the social desirability of an investment decision by systematically comparing the societal benefits it brings with the resources needed to produce it in order to assess the net welfare change attributable to it (Giffoni and Vignetti 2019). It is a worldwide recognised approach to

³ <https://hal.science/>

⁴ <https://www.openedition.org/>

evaluate public investments in different sectors, especially for infrastructure projects. The scoping review shows several attempts to apply CBA, or some aspects of it, to some specific initiatives. It is however often combined with other approaches in multi-method framework. CBA considers both financial and economic elements, which are distinguished as the cost and revenue aspects of the project (financial) and the benefits and costs to social welfare driven by the project (economic) (Delugas et al. 2025).

Cost-Benefit Analysis Framework: Key Principles

Traditional CBA incorporates four fundamental principles: long-term perspective (typically 10-30 years), incremental approach through counterfactual comparison, monetization of impacts using social opportunity costs rather than market prices, and microeconomic focus to avoid double-counting. This framework enables comprehensive social welfare assessment beyond simple financial analysis.

The innovative approach for CBA of Open Science developed within PathOS is based on the key principles of established CBA and adapt them to the specificity of the context. This framework is aimed at filling the existing gap on methodology ensuring a rigorous and consistent approach in measuring the impacts of Open Science. It does so by considering two key aspects: 1) the systematic comparison of benefits and costs and, 2) the comparison of the Open Science practice with a scenario where the same practice is not available. Although the benefits of Open Science may seem distinct in theory, their empirical measurement often reveals significant overlap due to their interrelated nature, necessitating careful appraisal to avoid double counting. The methodological framework developed by PathOS indicates which types of costs and benefits should be considered and how they should be measured and aggregated in order to achieve a rigorous assessment. It is designed to support the appraisal of short-term outcomes arising from Open Science initiatives and practices.

Taking this approach, CBA considers governments and funders, industry, researchers and/or citizens as potential beneficiaries; social costs including setup and maintenance costs; and the benefits gained by society mainly in the form of cost savings (social benefits). Long-term outcomes related to wider benefits, especially of enablement effects, cannot be systematically assessed within the CBA framework unless they can be clearly attributed to the corresponding costs (Delugas et al. 2025).

To conduct a CBA focused on the ELIXIR and RCAAP case studies, as described in detail in Deliverable 4.4 (Catalano et al. 2025a), the PathOS team conducted desk research focused on (1) historical and performance analysis literature focused on the resources under assessment to elucidate impact pathways and stakeholders involved as both beneficiaries and those incurring costs; (2) published and internal documents providing already established evidence

of impact created by the resources under assessment; and (3) evaluations of similar resources that provided methodological development.

Figure 5. Cost-benefit analysis framework in a nutshell

Following this, the PathOS team conducted online surveys with resource users to develop an understanding of their profiles, why they use the resources, alternative resources, and their perceived value of these resources. Building on these surveys, the PathOS team then conducted interviews with selected academic and industrial users for the ELIXIR case to gather greater detail about user behaviour, costs and benefits, and with users of RCAAP and with service providers of various research infrastructures to deepen our understanding of the terrain developed during desk research. Additionally, focus groups conducted during each case study were used to validate survey results (ELIXIR) and the CBA results (RCAAP). Finally, the PathOS team conducted citation and patent analysis to explore the long-term impacts of both resources under assessment. Findings from both CBA studies are incorporated into the synthesis of academic, societal and economic impacts, presented in Chapters 3-5.

The CBA of UniProt and RCAAP highlight key challenges in applying the CBA framework to Open Science. First, accurately defining the legal and functional boundaries of such resources is essential, yet complex, given their integration with external datasets and community contributions, as seen in UniProt and RCAAP. Second, evaluating the added value of these resources requires constructing a plausible counterfactual scenario, which is difficult due to the

absence of equivalent alternatives that replicate their full functionality. Finally, estimating the population impacted by costs and benefits is inherently imprecise, as open resources rarely track individual users; reliance on IP-based data yields conservative, lower-bound estimates due to shared or dynamic usage patterns and indirect beneficiaries.

Despite these challenges, these case studies demonstrate the substantial potential of CBA to provide robust evidence and a structured approach to impact, underscoring the importance of continued refinement in evaluation methodologies. Further methodological details, and findings, are presented in Deliverable 4.4 (Catalano et al. 2025a).

2.6. Stage 6: Validate model

Two key activities took place during Stage 6, designed to validate the conceptual framework developed during Stage 2 and create evidence-based Open Science impact pathways based on the evidence accumulated during Stages 1 and 4 and in relation to the Open Science Impact Indicators developed in Stage 3. These activities include (1) the development of Key Impact Pathways (KIP) driven by Open Science interventions, and (2) a synthesis of all PathOS generated evidence to validate the conceptual framework and establish evidence-based pathways to academic, societal and economic impacts driven by Open Science.

Key Open Science Impact Pathways

This task took a **qualitative approach to designing KIPs based on accumulated PathOS evidence** (scoping reviews and case studies) to propose quantitative measures (indicators) that can be used to identify causal relationships between Open Science interventions and certain outcomes and impacts. As described in Deliverable 1.3 (Karasz et al. 2024), this task deployed the conceptual framework presented in Deliverable 1.1 (Dekker et al. 2023) to establish evidence-based KIPs. Key impact pathways were understood to be those that are “the most important or relevant” for achieving Open Science impact (Dekker et al. 2023).

The PathOS team carried out this work by (1) collecting data that demonstrates causal links in the impact pathway (from the project scoping reviews and case studies) and coding it as corresponding to the relevant state of the impact pathway (activities, outputs, outcomes or impacts (academic, societal or economic)); (2) visualising impact pathways emanating from individual Open Science practices, linking them to PathOS impact indicators, and engaging the project consortium and key external stakeholders in validating this work; (3) enriching the impact pathways with detailed contextual information to articulate underlying assumptions and influential factors, and with other project findings. The approach, derived from Wilkinson et al. (2021), allows the use of both an “upstream” and a “downstream” analysis of causal

relationships between impacts and Open Science practices. An “upstream” analysis starts with a selected impact and identifying the interventions which can lead up to it. The downstream analysis, on the other hand, identifies the effects and eventual impacts which may occur downstream of an Open Science practice.

This task resulted in the identification of the following evidence-based, downstream causal impact pathways:

- **Citizen Science** leads to **societal impacts** on the environment, climate, health, and education.
- **Open Access** publishing leads to **academic impact** in terms of research quality; **societal impact** in terms of equity, policy and governance, and attainment of SDGs; and **economic impact** in terms of costs, innovation productivity, economic growth, and labour market.
- **Open/FAIR Data** leads to academic impact in terms of trust and citations; **economic impact** in terms of cost savings, uptake by industry, labour market impacts, innovation, and economic growth; and **societal impact** in terms of uptake by societal actors, and contributions toward SDGs.
- **Open code and software** leads to academic impact in terms of trust and citations; **economic impact** in terms of cost savings, uptake by industry, labour market impacts, innovation, and economic growth; and **societal impact** in terms of uptake by societal actors, and contributions toward SDGs.

And the following upstream impact pathways, which aid the identification of interventions in support of a specific impact:

- **Environmental impact** may be driven by **Open Access** publishing, **Citizen Science**, and **Open/FAIR data**; however, evidence is limited for these effects.
- **Reproducibility** is fostered by all Open Science practices.

These are presented in detail in an updated version of D1.3 (Stoy et al. 2025) and integrated into our project synthesis through a discussion of key findings presented in Chapter 6 of this report.

Project synthesis

This task, the final one of the PathOS, aimed to synthesis findings from across the project, and in doing so, to validate and articulate evidence-based Open Science Impact Pathways. In addition, and based on these synthesised findings, this task oversaw the development of recommendations for increasing Open Science impact (presented in Chapter 7). We took **a co-design approach** to both aspects of this task, hosting workshops for the project consortia to

define the synthesis and recommendations processes and aims, and to validate initial findings. We **engaged external expert stakeholders** in a validation process of synthesised findings and draft recommendations (through a hybrid event that took place in Paris at the UNESCO headquarters on 7 July 2025⁵) and through a second round of online validation of the revised recommendations with selected stakeholders. The recommendations presented in Chapter 7 were created primarily by the PathOS consortia with some contributions and revisions from stakeholders at the Paris event.

The work of this task was carried out primarily through desk research and involved the extraction of findings from relevant key project outputs (scoping reviews, case studies, CBA exercises, and indicators) that were organised into academic, societal and economic impact pathways. We took both a narrative and visual approach to this work, aligning evidence through both processes with the impact pathway nodes of activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts. To this work we applied the conceptual framework of Open Science mechanisms presented in Chapter 1 of this report and organised our presentation of synthesised findings in accordance with this understanding of Open Science, as primarily functioning to create access to research outputs, transparency of the research process, and participation of diverse actors in academic research. We then illustrate, through evidence and with relevance to Open Science indicators, how these lead to certain outcomes and academic, societal, and economic impacts (presented in Chapters 3–5 of this report). In reporting synthesised findings in these chapters, we provide **assessment of the strength of the evidence** presented for each outcome or impact, paying attention to the size of the body of evidence, the presence or absence of causal evidence, and whether controls were used. Our three-tier evidence quality system is defined as follows:

- **STRONG EVIDENCE:** Multiple studies, causal evidence, controlled comparisons
- **MODERATE EVIDENCE:** Limited studies, correlational evidence, reasonable controls
- **LIMITED EVIDENCE:** Single cases, speculative connections, no controls

Finally, we considered the interactions between academic, societal and economic realms and their relationship to the KIPs developed in the first part of this stage, described above (and presented in Chapter 6). In what follows, we present the findings from this task, as well as a discussion of their significance, concluding thoughts, and recommendations for increasing Open Science impact.

⁵ <https://pathos-project.eu/conference-on-open-science-monitoring-progress-assessing-impact>

3. Academic impact pathways

Definition of academic impact driven by Open Science

We define academic impact with Ravenscroft et al. as “the impact that scientific research has within the academic sphere” (Ravenscroft et al. 2017), hence distinguishing it from broader impacts upon society or the economy. Impacts are “long-lasting, elementary and wide-spread change” that result from the implementation of Open Science practices and process. They can be either “direct or indirect, intended or unintended, [and] relate to behavioural and/or systemic changes” (Dekker et al. 2023).

Pathways of academic impact

Our results show that Open Science has a range of academic impacts, from increased citations and research quality to equity and efficiency. However, most evidence is context-specific, with variation across disciplines, Open Science modes, and local conditions. Many findings remain correlational rather than definitively causal, and certain effects may be inconsistent or specific to certain disciplines or other contexts. Table 2 below summarises these findings (column B), with the intended effects represented for comparison.

Table 2. Comparison of intended academic impacts and summarised findings of impact

OS outputs (mechanisms)	A. Intended academic impacts	B. Summary of our findings
<i>Access</i>	Increased access to outputs is intended to spur academic innovation in the form of greater reuse of publications, data, algorithms and methods. Equity and inclusion are key foreseen benefits, in terms of levelling the playing field by giving disadvantaged actors greater access to these outputs to use as inputs for their own research activities. However, benefits are also framed by reference to return-on-investment and efficiency of the overall system.	Open Science speeds and broadens knowledge sharing and reduces redundant efforts and costs. Access to scientific knowledge seems to have positive effects (measured in terms of citations and reuse) upon the use of that knowledge.
<i>Transparency</i>	Increased transparency is intended to diminish questionable research	Open Science encourages transparency and accountability, although ethical risks

OS outputs (mechanisms)	A. Intended academic impacts	B. Summary of our findings
	<p>practices and enable downstream checks by opening information on the who, what, why, when, and how of research processes. This is often achieved through sharing of outputs but need not be. Quality and credibility of research are the ultimate aims, as well as increased trust and integrity amongst researchers.</p>	<p>remain. Open Science promotes reproducibility, but practical outcomes depend on effective implementation. Increased transparency shows some evidence of increasing quality of knowledge, which may in turn have effects upon use (given increased trust).</p>
<p><i>Participation</i></p>	<p>Increased participation is intended to make research more equitable and efficient through the empowerment of a greater range of research and non-academic actors to increase the scope and efficiency of research activities. Digital ICTs can connect people in new ways, and it has been hoped this will foster great global collaboration.</p>	<p>Open Science facilitates interdisciplinary and cross-sector collaborations, though impacts vary with context. Increased participation fosters new methods of data collection (especially via Citizen Science) and the wider accessibility and reuse, underpinning interdisciplinarity and collaboration; however, persisting structural inequalities may shape possibilities for participation in unexpected ways, meaning that equity must be closely monitored.</p>

Academic Impacts of Open Science

Figure 6. Diagrammatic presentation of the impact pathways for academic impact

Our pathways (Figure 6) show routes to:

- **Quality:** Open Science enhances quality in the sense of research rigour by contributing to methodological *transparency*. This output can result in outcomes like *reproducibility* (although practical outcomes depend on effective implementation), as well as promoting *ethics and integrity* (although increased transparency can also pose new ethical risks, e.g., for sensitive data).
- **Efficiency & Productivity:** Open Science speeds knowledge sharing and reduces redundant efforts and costs by enabling greater *re-use* of research outputs (especially as measured via *citations*) and sustaining the long-term visibility of research topics over time.
- **Equity, Diversity & Inclusion:** Open Science has potential equity benefits through increased *participation* of research actors (including greater scope for *collaboration* and *interdisciplinarity*), but may inadvertently disadvantage under-resourced groups (e.g., exclusion due to lack of resources in APC Open Access).

In the following sections, we break down our detailed findings regarding these aspects of impact. Academic impact represents the most well-developed domain within the PathOS OS Impact Indicator Handbook, reflecting the maturity of bibliometric methods, which enables the more comprehensive evidence synthesis that follows. Drawing on evidence from across PathOS activities (scoping review, impact indicators, empirical case studies, and cost-benefit analysis), we identify mechanisms linking Open Science to impacts in the academic sphere and explore challenges in establishing causal attribution.

3.1. Pathways to efficiency and productivity

Efficiency and productivity gains within the academic sphere were reported related to the speed of knowledge diffusion through earlier sharing of outputs and efficacy/scope of data collection. (Note that effects on efficiency and productivity in the broader economy are addressed in Chapter 5). Within **Open Access**, there is **strong evidence** that immediate availability of research can speed up knowledge diffusion and citation accrual. Preprints further enhance timeliness, especially during public health emergencies (e.g., rapid dissemination of COVID-19 studies). Reuse of **Open/FAIR Data & Code** can reduce duplication of effort and accelerate scientific progress. Although initial costs of data management and curation can be high, **limited evidence** demonstrates significant cost-savings in the long run. Within **Citizen Science** there is **strong evidence** that engaging large numbers of diverse volunteers can expand data collection over vast geographical and temporal scales at relatively low cost. Again, start-up costs (recruitment, training, infrastructure) can be significant, but net productivity gains emerge in longer or larger-scale projects. Finally, efficiencies can be attributed to **Open Methods**, where

common protocols and preregistrations can streamline research planning and reduce the risk of redundant work.

We can further elaborate in-depth findings on **citations** and **reuse**, as ways of gauging the extent to which Open Science enables researchers to build on each other's work, hence contributing to the *efficiency and productivity* of cumulative science, with new research building on and integrating past findings).

Citations

As described in Section 1.1, the key rationale for enabling greater *access* to research outputs is to unlock unrealised value through greater use and reuse, to hence raise the *efficiency* and *productivity* of research. Within academia, citations have a long history as a central measure of scientific importance. They are taken to be acknowledgement of the “intellectual and cognitive influences of scientific peers” (Bornmann and Daniel 2008), with references in scholarly works taken as proxies for academic impacts indicating influence, visibility, and intellectual connections. Within our scoping review, citations were the most documented impact type, accounting for almost a third of all included studies.

Overall, many aspects of Open Science are associated with increases in citations, although results are often inconsistent and sensitive to discipline. Within Open Access, studies frequently report an “Open Access Citation Advantage,” but the size (or even presence) of this effect varies widely across studies. *Green* and *Hybrid OA* often show more consistent citation advantages than *Gold OA*, possibly because many Gold-OA journals are newer and less established (**strong evidence**). Preprints can increase visibility, and potentially citations, though the mechanism may be confounded by self-selection (with higher-impact more likely to be preprinted) (**moderate evidence**). For Open/FAIR Data, there is **strong evidence** that providing openly accessible datasets is associated with higher citation counts for accompanying publications (estimates generally range from about 9 to 25% but have been found to be over 200% in some fields). At least part of this advantage may stem from direct citations by those who reuse the shared data. Some studies also suggest a minor citation advantage for publications with Open Code/Software while others observe no substantial effect, although there only a few studies on this topic. Finally, regarding Open Evaluation, articles with open peer review reports sometimes receive more attention and citations, especially in broader (less selective) citation databases, though results are inconsistent. At least part of this advantage may stem from direct citations by those who reuse the shared data. Some studies also suggest a minor citation advantage for publications with Open Code/Software while others observe no substantial effect, although there only a few studies on this topic. Finally, regarding Open Evaluation, articles with open

peer review reports sometimes receive more attention and citations, especially in broader (less selective) citation databases, though results are inconsistent (**limited evidence**).

In terms of mechanisms, such increases in citations are likely associated with the increased accessibility and availability of Open Access publications compared to closed publications. Citation advantages for papers with associated open outputs (data, code, reviews) may however also reflect increased perceptions of quality (see above), although since overall effects are often slight this may be difficult to measure authoritatively.

PathOS Open Science Impact **Indicator Handbook** (henceforth “Handbook”) contains the key indicator [Citation impact](#). The indicator provides a relatively clear measure of how open practices might influence research visibility and uptake, focusing primarily on citations to scholarly publications (e.g., journal articles). Caution is advised that in many circumstances, normalisation for differences across fields and publication year will be needed to allow fruitful comparison. The indicator is a crucial starting point for measuring the relationship between Open Science practices and research impact, since citations to journal articles are a well-established metric of scholarly influence, allowing comparisons across time and (when properly normalised) across disciplines. In addition, the Handbook includes citation-related indicators for non-traditional research outputs such as [Use of code in research](#) and [Use of data in research](#). The Handbook details the current state-of-the-art, cautioning that citation standards and supporting information infrastructures for monitoring require further development. Future iterations of the Handbook could further develop citation indicators for other Open Science output types including open peer review materials, research workflows, and protocols. Combined with traditional citation metrics, this could then enable ongoing monitoring of citation advantages.

Implementing such indicators, the **PathOS case studies** provide new empirical evidence of citation advantages linked to Open Science practices, employing innovative methodological approaches including AI-driven analysis, mixed-methods integration, and systematic attention to causality considerations. The **Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence** case investigated differences in citations and topic persistence in research on AI-for-climate between closed access and Green or Gold/Hybrid/Diamond OA (excluding publications that fall in both categories). Using propensity-score matching, the case study found an advantage of citations for Green OA over closed access, but no substantive difference between Gold/Hybrid/Diamond OA and closed access. The case study also revealed that Green OA significantly extends **topic persistence** over time (a new indicator measuring research area sustainability), helping sustain research areas in the literature longer, while Gold/Hybrid/Diamond OA showed weaker or even negative effects on long-term topic vitality.

The **Portuguese Repository Infrastructure RCAAP** case study found higher citation rates for articles deposited in the repository compared to other sources, though without controlling for

confounders. The repository effects case demonstrated that repository choice affects subsequent citation patterns and academic visibility. The **ELIXIR's Bioinformatics Resources** case found that using publicly accessible bioinformatics resources enhances citation impact among users. The **French Open Access Infrastructure** developed a novel '**Open Access advantage**' indicator using server log analysis and documented measurable access advantages for Open Science publications over closed publications across disciplines and countries - finding a distinctive access advantage that suggests enhanced visibility leading to potential citation benefits.

Reuse

Studies related to reuse in our literature scoping showed that, for **Open/FAIR Data Code**, public repositories enable repeated or novel uses of the same dataset or software (**strong evidence**). However, incomplete metadata, undocumented code, and mismatched data formats hinder real-world reuse (**limited evidence**). For **Citizen Science**, meanwhile, volunteer-collected data can be combined across regions or years, offering unique longitudinal or large-scale insights. Reuse of such data is maximised when data are properly curated and shared through established platforms. Finally, considering **Open Methods**, shared study protocols (e.g., preregistrations, registered reports) lay the groundwork for replication and extension. In practice, reuse requires data and code to be simultaneously available.

Within the PathOS Handbook, there are indicators for [Reuse of code in research](#) and [Reuse of data in research](#), which both aim to enable monitoring of the extent to which research utilises existing code/data in new research processes. In addition, the indicator [Prevalence of replication studies](#) functions as a potential indicator regarding extent to which original studies are reproduced by subsequent studies, as a special instance of re-use. These indicators empowered our case studies.

The **PathOS case studies** validate these literature findings while revealing additional patterns. The Impact of **Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications** case demonstrated large-scale adoption of structured sharing and referencing of datasets and software, with successful artifact reuse generating modest gains in cross-sector collaboration and interdisciplinary visibility, particularly when paired with high quality and early dissemination. The **Effects of Data Repositories on Data Usage** case examined reuse patterns in Social Sciences and Humanities through articles sampled from Scopus. Findings suggest moderate reuse levels, with 30% of articles reusing data. Confirming literature concerns about repository limitations, reused data almost exclusively came from public institutions (ministries, bureaus of statistics) rather than data repositories, highlighting how institutional context and data accessibility shape reuse patterns. The **ELIXIR UniProt CBA** demonstrated intensive reuse enabled by high-quality

curation. With approximately 100,000 annual users (67% academic), the platform generates substantial time savings: 10 hours/week for labour time, 6.8 hours/week for access time and 5.4 hours for transaction time for new users. Benefits exceed costs by a factor of seven, with 65% of users reporting that academic publication drafting would be slower without UniProt. This validates literature findings that proper curation maximizes reuse potential.

These cases collectively confirm that while Open Science enables reuse, the extent of reuse, and resulting productivity gains, depends critically on data quality, institutional context, and infrastructure design, reinforcing the literature's emphasis on addressing metadata, documentation, and accessibility barriers.

3.2. Pathways to quality

Raising the quality of research is commonly accepted as a core aim of Open Science (see Sec. 1.1). Quality is, however, a somewhat abstract concept that can be taken to refer to methodological soundness (whether in terms of rigour, credibility, integrity) as well as originality or novelty. The PathOS Indicator Handbook entry on [Quality](#) emphasises caution, describing it as a multidimensional concept that is usually best judged through peer review. Some research shows correlations with citations, depending on the level of study and aggregation (more suited for evaluation of institutions than individuals, for example). Other relevant indicators include the (somewhat speculative and difficult to operationalise) Reproducibility indicator [Inclusion in Systematic Reviews or Meta-Analyses](#), where since such reviews often include risk of bias assessments or other quality control mechanisms, the inclusion of papers within such reviews could be taken as some indicator of quality. In addition, [Reuse of data in research](#) and [Reuse of Code in research](#) could also be taken as indicators of rigour, in as much as methods and processes described in research publications are transparent and accessible. Future developments could develop benchmark indicators for quality of Citizen Science data, quality of Open Methods materials, etc.

In our **scoping review**, we found that almost a quarter of included studies report findings related to the impact of Open Science on research quality. Many of these related to studies analysing the quality of data collected via Citizen Science. In **Citizen Science**, the quality of volunteer-collected data is frequently comparable to professional data, provided adequate training and protocols are in place (**strong evidence**). Study design and oversight are typically more decisive for data quality than whether collectors are amateurs or professionals. Overall, while open practices show potential to increase quality, evidence is mixed and context-dependent, with mediating factors such as editorial standards, documentation practices, and study design often playing a decisive role. Regarding **Open Access**, no intrinsic difference in methodological rigour has been definitively shown between Open Access and non-Open Access

journals, although mixed findings exist regarding article quality (**moderate evidence**). “Predatory journals” remain a marginal concern but reflect a potential threat to quality if editorial standards are lax. Sharing of **Open/FAIR Data & Code** can strengthen quality if others are therefore able to replicate or extend results. However, quality gains are limited when datasets/codes are incomplete or poorly documented. Finally, within **Open Methods**, structured preregistration, registered reports, and transparent protocols are linked to fewer questionable research practices (e.g., selective reporting), indicating a potential quality improvement. This **limited evidence** is derived from relatively small-scale or pilot studies, however, so further assessment is needed to confirm broader efficacy.

In addition to these findings, other results related to *ethics and integrity* and *reproducibility* are relevant, as we explain next.

Ethics and integrity

Ethics and integrity in research are essential to ensure the quality of research. Open Science contributes to this in so far as *transparent processes* (via, e.g., **Open Access, Open/FAIR Data, Open Methods** and **Open Evaluation**) can encourage greater accountability and hence reduce questionable practices. However, evidence of effects in this regard is mixed. Our scoping review found open peer review reports and open identities to have an unclear impact on the integrity of the review process, with some studies reporting positive impacts, while others report no impact. There are also risks of participant re-identification in sensitive datasets if personal information is inadvertently shared. The literature further recognises community-driven data governance (e.g., indigenous data sovereignty) as being critical for respecting diverse ethical norms. Finally, “predatory publishing” and concerns about retaliation in open review remain ethical challenges. The PathOS Indicator Handbook does not yet include indicators related to ethics and integrity, and it is suggested this may be a core area for future improvement.

Reproducibility

In many quantitative disciplines, poor levels of reproducibility have been seen to threaten the quality of research. Although this is controversial, with commentators warning that reproducibility must not be seen as a marker of quality for all kinds of research, especially those qualitative domains that rely upon interpretative judgement (Leonelli 2018; Cole, Ulpts, Bochynska, Kormann, Good, and Ross-Hellauer 2024), nonetheless many Open Science advocates from the *transparency* tradition (Section 1.1) see raising levels of reproducibility as a way to improve quality (Munafo et al. 2017).

From our scoping review, we find that **Open/FAIR Data & Code** theoretically boosts reproducibility. In practice, however, many shared datasets/codes are incomplete, mislabelled, or lack good documentation. Actual reproducibility often hinges on contacting original authors for clarifications (**moderate evidence**). In **Open Methods**, preregistration can reduce undisclosed changes to methodology or data analysis, thus improving transparency (**moderate evidence**). Actual replication success rates vary. Some replication attempts uncover the complexity, and time demands of re-running another team's experiments.

The PathOS Indicator Handbook includes a dedicated section on reproducibility, including the indicators: [Consistency in reported numbers](#), [Impact of Open Code in Research](#), [Impact of Open Data in Research](#), [Inclusion in Systematic Reviews or Meta-Analyses](#), [Level of replication](#), [Prevalence of open/FAIR data practices](#), [Prevalence of Open Methods practices](#), and [Prevalence of replication studies](#).

3.3. Pathways to equity, diversity & inclusion

Within our **Indicator Handbook**, the indicator [Diversity](#) distinguishes three ways of addressing diversity: diversity of topics, diversity of scholars' demographics, and diversity in terms of outputs (e.g., bibliodiversity). We also emphasise the importance of our indicator on [APC costs](#) for monitoring who is able to pay for Open Access publishing, a key risk flagged during our evidence scoping. In general, further development of indicators for Equity, Diversity & Inclusion could be considered a key priority for future development of the Handbook.

Results from our scoping review highlighted significant risks for equity for marginalised communities. Considering **Open Science in general**, access to resources (training, infrastructure, administrative support) is unevenly distributed, risking a tiered system where only wealthier institutions can fully adopt Open Science practices. Within **Open Access**, APC-based funding models often exclude or disadvantage underfunded researchers (especially in the Global South), undermining equitable participation in Open Access publishing (**strong evidence**). Fee-waiver policies rarely solve the problem comprehensively. **Limited evidence** indicates greater diversity of citations in Open Access. For **Open/FAIR Data**, meanwhile, unequal infrastructure, skills, and internet connectivity limit who truly benefits from Open Datasets (**moderate evidence**). Ethical frameworks like CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, and Ethics) are also needed for ethical governance of indigenous or community data. Considering **Citizen Science**, projects often concentrate in the Global North and may not engage marginalised communities who may have less free time if unpaid (**limited evidence**). Co-creation and proper crediting of volunteers as well as financial compensation to ensure diversity are ongoing challenges to inclusive participation. Finally, in **Open Evaluation** (specifically Open Peer Review), junior scholars, women, and marginalised researchers may feel

less comfortable signing reviews, raising concerns about skewed representation among reviewers. Although empirical evidence is still limited, theoretical arguments warn of potential power imbalances.

However, **PathOS case studies** reveal a complex picture, demonstrating both challenges and opportunities for inclusion. The **Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence** case found that Published OA (Diamond/Gold/Hybrid OA) correlates with modest gains in gender equity, particularly in increasing the share of women in senior author positions. However, Green Open Access showed a small decline in all-women author teams, highlighting complex dynamics between different openness pathways and inclusion. More broadly, PathOS case studies demonstrate positive outcomes including enhanced collaboration intensity and interdisciplinary research connections enabled by open infrastructure, suggesting that well-designed Open Science systems can support inclusive participation when implementation barriers are addressed.

Collaboration

Open Science's potential to enable new modes of collaboration holds potential for equity as it may enable inclusion (or exclusion). Our literature review revealed surprisingly **limited evidence** regarding effects of Open Science on collaboration. Regarding **Open Science in general**, many Open Science networks and platforms exist to forge interdisciplinary and cross-institutional research ties. Real-world adoption depends on researchers' digital literacy, incentives, and the willingness of institutions to support open practices. Within **Open/FAIR Data & Code**, sharing can draw collaborators who can adapt or improve existing materials. Large, international collaborations (e.g., meta-analyses, multi-site projects) increasingly rely on open standards and common platforms. **Citizen Science**, meanwhile, is collaborative in its essence, bringing diverse stakeholders into scientific processes, occasionally generating novel questions or solutions (**moderate evidence**). Challenges revolve around coordinating volunteers, ensuring data consistency, and recognising contributor roles.

The Indicator Handbook defines the indicator [Collaboration intensity](#) to enable measurement of authors, institutes or countries involved in collaborations, as well as collaborative publications. Our CBA focused on **ELIXIR's UniProt** resource that shared datasets foster interdisciplinarity, and over half of surveyed users said that academic sector collaboration would be slower if UniProt did not exist (Catalano et al. 2025c).

3.4. Lessons learned

Our synthesis of findings on the academic impacts of Open Science practices shows a wide range of academic benefits, with the most attention given to Open Access, citizen participation in research, and the sharing of research data. Most of the evidence relates to increased citation rates, improvements in research efficiency, and enhanced research quality. Positive impacts include higher citation levels for Open Access publications (though effects vary by type and discipline), cost savings and broader data collection through citizen involvement, and greater reuse and reproducibility of shared data. However, the evidence also shows mixed or limited effects on aspects such as article quality, editorial processes, and statistical robustness. Negative impacts are reported in relation to equity and inclusion, with financial and technical barriers limiting who can publish in Open Access journals or reuse shared data, especially for researchers from less-resourced contexts. Ethical risks, such as data misuse and lack of benefit-sharing, are also noted. These impacts are linked to specific pathways, such as increased visibility driving reuse in the case of Open Access and data sharing, or efficiencies from broader participation in citizen research. However, these mechanisms are moderated by enabling and inhibiting factors, including the availability of skills, infrastructure, institutional support, and the compatibility of open practices with different research traditions.

Our analysis reveals key research gaps:

- **Beyond Citation Advantage in Open Access:** Research on Open Access benefits is heavily skewed toward citation advantages simply because citation data is readily available and easy to analyse. This 'streetlight effect' means we know much more about citation patterns than about whether Open Access actually reaches intended beneficiaries or enables knowledge use in practice.
- **Quality of shared research outputs:** While availability of data and code is often tracked, there is limited empirical work evaluating their actual quality. More rigorous assessments are needed to understand the standards, completeness, and reusability of shared research materials.
- **Efficiency of Open Science workflows:** There is a notable gap in research examining how Open Science practices (e.g., data/code sharing, open peer review) affect the overall efficiency of the research process. Studies should address both potential gains and unintended inefficiencies introduced by open workflows. The CBA methods developed within PathOS form a solid methodological enabler. Prevalence of such studies would enable macroeconomic modelling.
- **Reuse and the role of data management practices:** The impact of data reuse is strongly influenced by the quality of data management and curation practices by original depositors. More research is needed on the effectiveness of Data Management Plans

(DMPs) and open methods in enhancing data quality, reusability, and research reproducibility.

- **Equity and capability in Open Science participation:** The effects of Open Science on equity require ongoing monitoring, particularly regarding disparities in the ability to participate in or benefit from Open Science. Research should focus on identifying and addressing capability gaps that may limit equitable access and contribution to Open Science practices.

PathOS contributes methodological advances that could enable future work to address these gaps. The project demonstrates evaluation approaches combining AI-driven computational analysis with mixed-methods integration, enabling research at scales and contexts previously difficult to achieve. All **PathOS case studies** are accompanied by open code, datasets, and detailed methodological documentation, providing tools and frameworks for other researchers to build upon.

Regarding issues of causality and attribution, establishing robust counterfactuals is particularly challenging since while it is quite straight forward to compare citations of Open Access and closed access, it is much harder to compare reuse of Open Data versus closed data, since closed data that has been re-used is hard to identify. Further methodological focus on such core questions including improved standards and guidelines for reporting is hence desirable.

4. Societal impact pathways

This synthesis consolidates findings from the PathOS project on the societal impact of Open Science practices. Drawing on a scoping review of published evidence (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024), a suite of impact indicators (Apartis et al. 2024), and empirical case studies (Stavropoulos et al. 2025a,b), this chapter illuminates how Open Science can lead to a variety of societal impacts. We demonstrate the mechanisms through which Open Science can generate societal benefits, identify the challenges in establishing causal attribution, and highlight findings from case studies. This synthesis of evidence from across the PathOS project provides insight into how evidence-based policy making can foster societal impacts driven by Open Science.

4.1. Societal impact pathways: a conceptual framework

Definition of societal impact driven by Open Science

We define societal impacts from Open Science as “long-lasting, elementary and wide-spread change” that result from the implementation of Open Science practices and process. They can be either “direct or indirect, intended or unintended, [and] relate to behavioural and/or systemic changes” (Dekker et al. 2023).

Pathways to societal impact

Societal impact pathways refer to the mechanisms through which Open Science practices generate impacts in society, both positive and negative. The PathOS project provides a conceptual foundation for understanding how Open Science may generate societal impact. As elaborated in the introduction of this report, we understand Open Science as enabling three key things: **access** to research outputs, **transparency** of the research process, and **participation** of diverse actors in research (see Figure 1). In terms of societal impact, we understand the goals to be as follows (Table 3):

Table 3. Comparison of intended societal impacts and summarised findings of impact

OS Mechanism	A. Intended societal impacts	B. Summary of our findings
Access	Increased access to research outputs is intended to make “scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone,” and facilitate the “sharing of information for the benefits of science and society” (UNESCO 2021a). It is believed that numerous societal benefits can flow from access to research outputs, as both societal and industrial actors can reuse them in ways that respond to societal challenges.	Open Science enables societal actors to access and reuse research outputs, which democratises scientific knowledge and drives societal impacts including empowerment of people and communities, benefits to the environment and climate, and to health and safety. When industrial actors reuse research outputs, societally relevant innovations may be produced.
Transparency	Increased transparency of the research process is not only thought to increase the trust in and credibility of research among researchers, but also among the public and societal actors.	<i>No findings</i>
Participation	Increased participation of societal actors throughout the research life cycle is intended to make research more equitable and societally relevant through the empowerment of a greater range of societal actors, which diversifies the viewpoints that shape research, its findings, applications and impacts (UNESCO 2021a).	Participatory research approaches, whether academically- or community-driven, democratise research, foster social ties and cohesion among participants and communities, enable reuse of research outputs by societal actors, drive increases in knowledge and awareness among participants and communities, foster behavioural change, and enable trust between stakeholders. Together, these outcomes lead to positive impacts on equity and empowerment, on the environment and climate, and in health and safety.

Our synthesis of the evidence identified two evidence-based impact pathways stemming from two Open Science mechanisms (Figure 7):

1. Participation: Citizen Science and other participatory and/or societally inclusive research processes lead directly to a variety of well-evidenced beneficial societal outcomes and impacts (**strong evidence**).

2. Access: Open outputs, including Open Access publications, Open/FAIR data, and open-source code/software, lead to a variety of societal impacts when they are reused by societal actors (**moderate evidence**).

Our review of the evidence shows that these pathways lead to **social (equity and empowerment), environmental, and health impacts**.

In what follows, we present detailed evidence from across the PathOS project to illustrate the **pathways to equity and empowerment, climate and environmental, and health and safety impacts**.

Societal Impacts of Open Science

Figure 7. Evidence-based Open Science societal impact pathways

4.2. Pathways to empowerment and equity

Through our scoping review focused on the societal impact of Open Science (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024), PathOS has established **moderate evidence** of empowerment and equity impacts driven by societal participation in research, namely through Citizen Science and other participatory approaches to research. When members of the **public are included in scientific research processes**, we see evidence of multiple outcomes that lead to these impacts: the creation and strengthening of **social ties and cohesion**, **reuse of related research outputs** by societal actors, the **democratisation of research**, increased **knowledge and awareness**, **behavioural change**, and the establishment of **trust between stakeholders** involved in societally inclusive research. Each of these **leads to either equity or empowerment**, or both. Additionally, we have some evidence, from both our scoping review and case studies (Stavropoulos et al. 2025a), that **societal access to research outputs**, driven by Citizen Science and Open Access publishing, **leads to empowerment and/or equity** by enabling societal reuse of research outputs. Here, we provide detail about these pathways to empowerment and equity.

Empowerment and equity impact from societal participation

Our scoping review found that Citizen Science **fosters social ties** between participants and other project stakeholders, forging new relationships, and can strengthen preexisting ones (**moderate evidence**). Participation in Citizen Science also strengthens connections to place and a sense of community (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 14) (**limited evidence**). All of this can be understood as **increasing social capital**, which refers to relationship networks that allow people and groups to achieve their goals. Cumulatively, by building and strengthening social ties and social capital, these outcomes **empower** participants and communities (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 14–18) (**moderate evidence**). It is important to note, however, that some evidence shows that participation in Citizen Science can weaken or harm social ties and community cohesion. This can occur when Citizen Science projects spark or enflame inter-group conflicts or when trust is not established among participants and project stakeholders (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 14) (**limited evidence**).

Societal participation in research also democratises research, which drives equity and empowerment. Evidence from our scoping review shows that participating in Citizen Science drives the **development of leadership capacity** and empowers participants to take **leadership positions** both within projects and their communities (**limited evidence**). Evidence shows that participation also **increases self-efficacy** among adults and children (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 14–18) (**strong evidence**). Democratisation can also lead to equity

impacts, like the **just redistribution of natural resources** or improvements to formerly neglected physical infrastructure (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 18) (**limited evidence**). However, in some cases, democratisation of research can undermine equity and empowerment. Some evidence shows that access to participate in Citizen Science is not always equitable, and in some cases, undue responsibility to respond to identified problems is placed on participants and their communities (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 18) (**limited evidence**).

Increases in knowledge and awareness, driven by societal participation, also lead to equity and empowerment impacts. **Strong evidence** shows that participating in Citizen Science leads to **growth in subject and general scientific knowledge**, and the **development of scientific skills** among participants, and creates positive change in knowledge and awareness at the community level (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 8). These changes represent an **equity impact in the distribution of scientific knowledge and skills**. Importantly, evidence also shows that there are certain characteristics of societal participation in research that foster positive outcomes and impacts. When participation is more in-depth, long-term, and interactive, greater increases in knowledge and awareness are produced (**moderate evidence**). Community-based projects are known drivers of increased scientific skills and knowledge, and evidence also shows that child participants are particularly effective at spreading knowledge gains within their communities (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 10) (**limited evidence**). Other research shows that changes in knowledge and awareness result in **community development and activism**, which we classify as **empowerment** impact (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 14) (**limited evidence**).

To measure impacts driven by societal participation in research, the PathOS Indicator Handbook offers [a suite of Citizen Science indicators](#) that can be used as proxies for these purposes (Apartis et al. 2024). Measuring the extent of societal participation across the research lifecycle, these indicators can be used individually or collectively to estimate impacts that stem from societal participation in research.

Equity impact from access to research outputs

Evidence from our scoping review and case studies show that **societal access to research outputs**, including Open Access publications and Open/FAIR data **enables reuse and may lead to equity impacts**. Our scoping review found evidence, generally reliant on Altmetrics-based research, that Open Access publications and books are referenced more frequently than closed literature in the news, on the web, on social media (where they generate more engagement), and in policy documents (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 18–19) (**moderate evidence**). However, we note that within this tranche of literature, studies that prove causality are scarce. Where we see potential for equity impacts is with Open Access books, where some research has found that they reach larger and more geographically diverse readers, and are more frequently

accessed, compared to closed books, in low- and middle-income countries (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 19) (**limited evidence**). However, actual demographic details on those accessing Open Access books were not available in this research. Therefore, based on the published evidence, we conclude that there is *potential* for Open Access publications to lead to equity impacts, but this is not yet proven.

PathOS' **French Open Access Infrastructure** case study provides empirical evidence of the access pathway by analysing user logs from OpenEdition and HAL platforms. The study found that **a diversity of public sector and business/industrial users access open resources**, with access advantages greater outside academia than within it (Stavropoulos et al. 2025a). The innovative "Open Access Advantage indicator" demonstrates openness creates measurable access advantages that vary significantly by country - some showing substantial advantages (USA 12%, India 9%, France 8%) while others, particularly Arab states, show considerable disadvantages (Iraq 60%, Sudan 57%, Libya 55%), potentially due to reliance on language-specific closed publications. This approach provides clearer demographic evidence of user diversity than Altmetrics-based studies and aligns with prior research showing Open Access broadens geographic reach (Ozaygen et al. 2020). However, the study cannot determine whether accessing resources translates to actual societal use, highlighting the challenge of measuring impact beyond access. The case study provide the basis for future research, which could use mixed-methods or qualitative approaches to investigate whether those who access these resources use them and to what ends.

4.3. Pathways to climate and environmental impact

Like the pathways to empowerment and equity described above, PathOS found **strong evidence** through our scoping review that Citizen Science and other participatory forms of research lead to climate and environmental impacts. By enabling **societal participation in research** and **societal access to research outputs**, Citizen Science leads to outcomes including **changes to knowledge, awareness and behaviour**, and the **reuse of research outputs** by societal actors. These, in turn, lead to climate and environmental impacts (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024) (**strong evidence**). To measure Open Science impacts on climate and environment, the PathOS Indicator Handbook offers [a general method for investigating uptake in and impact on societal issues](#) (Apartis et al. 2024). One could use this method to investigate these types of impacts, as well as myriad others. Here, we provide detail about these pathways to climate and environmental impact.

Climate and environmental impact from societal participation

By enabling societal participation in research, Citizen Science and other participatory forms of research can foster outcomes that include **changes to knowledge, awareness and behaviour**, and **reuse of research outputs**. Evidence shows that these, in turn, **lead to climate and environmental impacts**. **Strong evidence** shows that participating in Citizen Science leads to positive changes in awareness, attitudes, and values related to climate and environment. These include things like awareness of how human behaviour impacts climate and environment, developing a sense of environmental stewardship, and a change in attitude toward the use of resources (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 10) (**strong evidence**). **Limited evidence** also suggests that pro-environmental behaviour change occurs because of these changes. Studies show evidence of changes to behaviour including the adoption of biodiversity-sensitive gardening practices, changes to waste management and consumption practices, and spreading awareness of these efforts (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 10–13). However, it may be the case that some Citizen Science participants are more likely to make behavioural changes than others, given predispositions like pre-existing pro-environmental attitudes or involvement in other initiatives. Others question the impact scale of behaviour changes that are private or personal, rather than public facing (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 13). Finally, evidence shows that Citizen Science projects and programmes, by empowering participants to act, can also drive climate and environmental impact by creating community-based monitoring that fills gaps in government services (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 13) (**moderate evidence**).

Climate and environmental impact from access to research outputs

By **enabling societal access to research outputs**, evidence shows Citizen Science and other participatory forms of research can **foster reuse of research outputs** in ways that **lead to climate and environmental impacts**. **Strong evidence** from our scoping review shows that data generated by Citizen Science projects has been used to inform the monitoring and management of natural resources, environmental pollution, and the built environment. For example, Citizen Science data has been used to create and monitor protected areas, respond to pollution events, and to inform environmental policy (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 13). In cases where project findings or data, and advocacy on the part of participants and communities is used to redress environmental or natural resource injustice, equity may follow as a downstream impact. However, other research shows that Citizen Science data is not always

accepted as valid by those in positions of power and so creating impact via this pathway can be challenging (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 13).

The PathOS case study on the **Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence** investigates whether Open Access publications may share this pathway to impact. Their findings show that Published Open Access papers (versus Green OA papers) have greater **alignment with SDG targets** than do closed-access publications. The study team therefore suggests that “journal-mediated openness connects research outputs more visibly to global sustainability agendas” (Stavropoulos 2025a).

Additionally, the case study found that **Green Open Access significantly extends the persistence of AI-for-climate research topics over time**, helping sustain these research areas in the literature longer than Published Open Access. While this represents an upstream rather than direct environmental impact, maintaining the research foundation for climate solutions could facilitate longer-term societal access and application for environmental benefit. This finding suggests that repository-based sharing may better support the sustained development of research areas critical to addressing environmental challenges.

While this finding is not evidence of societal impact, it establishes ground for further investigation of what happens post-publication. Do societal or industrial actors take up these outputs and use them in ways that create positive climate and environmental impact? These questions have yet to be examined, but our research suggests that they should be.

These two indicators - SDG alignment and topic persistence for climate-relevant research - represent **proxy measures** that offer a practical methodological solution for investigating societal impacts when direct impact data is unavailable or difficult to obtain. Similar to the French case study's use of access patterns, PathOS demonstrates how advanced AI-driven analysis and mixed-methods approaches can **develop upstream indicators** that trace reasonable pathways to societal benefit. While we do not claim these represent direct societal impact, they provide **evidence-based foundations** for impact assessment as the field develops more robust direct measurement approaches. This methodological innovation enables systematic investigation of potential societal pathways that would otherwise remain unexplored due to measurement challenges.

4.4. Pathways to health and safety impacts

PathOS found **moderate evidence**, through our scoping review and case studies, that Open Science leads to health and safety impacts. By enabling **societal participation in research**, Citizen Science leads to outcomes including **changes to knowledge, awareness and behaviour**, and the **reuse of research outputs** by societal actors (**strong evidence**). These, in

turn, lead to health and safety impacts. By **enabling access to research outputs**, a **limited amount of evidence** shows that **Open Access publishing, and the sharing of data, software, code and tools** lead to **reuse by societal actors**, which leads to **health impacts**. The PathOS Indicator Handbook (Apartis et al. 2024) offers two specific indicators for measuring health impact: [Uptake in medical practice](#), and [Uptake by patient groups](#). Additionally, the general method developed by PathOS for measuring [Uptake in and impact on societal issues](#) can be operationalised to study health-related issues.

Health and safety impact from societal inclusion

By enabling societal participation in research, Citizen Science and other participatory forms of research can foster outcomes that include **changes to knowledge, awareness and behaviour**, and **reuse of research outputs (strong evidence)**, which are shown to **lead to health and safety impacts (moderate evidence)**. Evidence from our scoping review (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024) shows that Citizen Science projects and programmes spread awareness of environmental and physical health risks and ways to mitigate them, and foster changes in behaviour that are beneficial to health (**moderate evidence**). For example, some research has found that Citizen Science air quality data is used by participants to make decisions about outdoor activity, and that programmes focused on air pollution led to participants cycling or walking instead of driving automobiles (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 18). There is also evidence that participating in Citizen Science can lead to negative health outcomes, when participants are placed in dangerous situations or when psychological trauma results from participating (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 18) (**limited evidence**).

Health and safety impact from access to research outputs

Across the PathOS project we have compiled **limited evidence** that **societal access to research outputs**, via Open Access publications, and the sharing of Open Code, Software and Tools **lead to reuse of research outputs by societal actors**, which **leads to health and safety impacts**. A limited amount of evidence from our scoping review shows that Open Access publishing leads to greater knowledge acquisition among healthcare professionals, which may impact decisions about treatment (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 19). We also found evidence that Open Access publishing may compromise patient privacy and healthcare and research ethics, when images of patients' bodies are shared openly without their consent (a negative health impact) (Marshall et al. 2018). Other research indicates that the impact of Open Access on health and healthcare is understudied (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024, 19).

Limited evidence exists for health impacts fostered by Open Code, Software and/or Tools. Our scoping review identified a couple of studies that show that these Open Research outputs,

when deployed in healthcare contexts, can lead to beneficial health impacts. Evidence shows that these tools have been used in low-income countries across the global south to improve the delivery of healthcare (Bokonda et al. 2019). This is a case where **equity may also be a downstream impact**, in terms of the equitable provision of access to and the delivery of healthcare to historically underserved populations. Another study found that Open-Source Software had a positive impact on epidemiology and public health management in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic (Kobayashi et al. 2021).

PathOS contributes to this evidence base with findings from its **Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications** case study, which investigated whether COVID-19 research papers whose datasets or software were subsequently reused by other researchers achieved greater clinical impact. Before accounting for confounding factors, papers whose artifacts were reused showed substantially higher clinical uptake - averaging 0.91 clinical trial citations versus 0.20 for non-reused papers. However, after controlling for study quality, citation exposure, publication timing, authorship patterns, and artifact volume, this advantage disappeared and even reversed slightly. Papers with reused artifacts showed modestly fewer clinical trial citations and guideline citations than expected based on their other characteristics.

Importantly, reuse effects varied significantly by research context. High-quality papers with strong field-weighted citation impact gained more clinical traction when their artifacts were reused, and early-pandemic publications benefited more than later ones. This suggests reuse acts as an amplifier of existing research strengths rather than an independent driver of clinical adoption. The findings indicate that in fast-moving health emergencies, clinical decision-makers prioritize research credibility, visibility, and timeliness over technical artifact reuse, revealing important limitations in assuming that open practices automatically translate to health benefits. This case study operationalised the [Uptake in medical practice](#) indicator developed by PathOS and described in the PathOS Indicator Handbook (Apartis et al. 2024).

4.5. Lessons learned

A synthesis of PathOS results regarding pathways to societal impact, drawing on our scoping review on the topic and findings from case studies, shows that both participation and access drive societal impact, but most of the evidence available is focused on impact driven by Citizen Science. Our research into this topic reveals that there is limited evidence of societal impact driven by Open Access publishing. This evidence is limited in terms of amount and design, in that what we have is based largely on Altmetric data. This evidence demonstrates engagement (sometimes reuse) but does not, in fact, give us evidence of *who* engages with these outputs, nor any societal impact that might follow these outcomes. Our case study focused on societal

engagement with French repositories removes web sharing as a mediator and shows us that a diversity of societal actors directly access open outputs through repositories, which affords some degree of demographic knowledge about these users. However, it too provides evidence of only an indicator of impact (access) and does not examine the context of reuse, nor the societal impact that may follow it.

Our synthesis of this evidence reveals that there is a lot that we still do not know about the societal impact of Open Science. The gaps in evidence revealed by our study include the following:

- **Access:** Does Open/FAIR Data have societal impact? Our scoping review, when conducted, found no published evidence that demonstrated societal impact from Open/FAIR Data. The evidence we included in our synthesis comes from just one PathOS case study focused on COVID-19. The findings from this case suggest that quality and visibility influence reuse more than openness. It remains an open question whether Open/FAIR Data create societal impact.
- **Access:** Do Open Code/Software/Tools have societal impact? Like the points made above about Open/FAIR data, our evidence includes just two publications and findings from our COVID-19 case study. The same questions apply here.
- **Transparency:** Does transparency of process, in particular Open Methods or Open Evaluation, have societal impact? PathOS was unable to find evidence in response to this question. While our scoping review found limited evidence that signalling Open Science (signally transparency) leads to greater engagement with open outputs and trust in science, questions remain as to whether transparency leads to societal impact. It is possible (in fact, likely) that transparency enables reuse by industrial and/or societal actors, which could lead to societal impact, but we do not yet have evidence of this pathway to impact.
- **Type of impact:** Our synthesis provides evidence of societal impact in terms of empowerment and equity, climate and environment, and health and safety, but not of other types of impact that we looked for when we scoped the literature. We lack evidence of societal impact in terms of social dynamics around gender, culture, sexuality, race, ethnicity, and geography. We also lack evidence of impact that aligns with SDGs beyond climate/environment and health.
- **Type of impact:** While we did find evidence of societal impact in the form of equity, we note that this evidence is limited and remains an understudied area of societal impact.

A key finding of our multi-method, interdisciplinary investigation of the societal impact of Open Science is that establishing evidence of societal impact is highly challenging. To do so, one must establish that Open Science in particular, rather than science in general, is influencing society. Teasing these two apart is challenging, to say the least. Citizen Science is the most studied Open

Science intervention, in terms of societal impact, because methods have been established for evaluating participants and communities before and after a project begins and ends. And, since researchers often establish close relationships with participants, other stakeholders, and communities through this process, they have insider knowledge of how project outputs or results may lead to impact. However, tracing the impact pathway of other Open Science outputs, including Open Access publications, Open/FAIR data, and Open Code/Software/Tools, is far more complex. To do so requires long-term, mixed methods research that first requires data about access and users before what happens with accessed outputs can be studied.

Our **French Open Access Infrastructure** study paves the way with a novel method for establishing evidence about access and users. Others may now implement this method to create a broad and multi-context evidence base of access and users. Then, the metascience community will be poised to investigate the next steps in the pathway to societal impact.

Additionally, PathOS demonstrates the value of developing **proxy indicators** when direct societal impact measurement remains challenging. Through innovative AI-driven analysis and mixed-methods approaches, PathOS developed upstream indicators such as SDG alignment of publications and topic persistence for climate-relevant research that trace reasonable pathways to potential societal benefit. While these **do not represent direct impact evidence**, they provide methodologically sophisticated approaches for investigating **potential societal pathways** that would otherwise remain unexplored due to measurement constraints. This proxy indicator approach offers a practical solution for advancing societal impact assessment while the field develops more robust direct measurement capabilities.

We elaborate on these challenges in greater detail in Chapter 6 of this report.

5. Economic impact pathways

This chapter consolidates emerging findings from the PathOS project on the economic impact of Open Science practices. Drawing on a structured scoping review, an impact indicators framework, and empirical case studies, it explores if, how and through which mechanisms Open Science generates economic impact. We also identify the challenges of establishing causal attribution and highlight insights from case studies. The analysis offers a pathway-based understanding to inform evidence-based policy on the economic value of Open Science.

5.1. Economic Impact Pathways: a conceptual framework

Definition of economic impact driven by Open Science

Economic impacts of Open Science are understood as the long-lasting changes in the economic sphere experienced by users of Open Science artifacts (academic and industrial researchers but also government, civil society, NGOs and society at large), processes and collaborations. We do not address the economics of the publishing sector and its business models⁶.

Economic impact measurement faces significant methodological challenges, as economic impact indicators remain less developed compared to academic metrics, and establishing causal attribution across longer time horizons is inherently difficult.

Pathways to economic impact

While theoretical arguments for economic impact are well-developed, empirical evidence has historically been limited.

- Economic rationale stems from the key concept of knowledge as a public good. The key argument is that Open Science increases research productivity and academic impact leads to economic consequences thanks to higher and quicker uptake of research results by other scientists in academia and industry, also thanks to science-industry collaboration. This process affects the private sector and ultimately drives societal impacts.
- There are also counterarguments: because individuals and companies want to benefit from the new knowledge they create, they may strategically delay publication and data sharing.

⁶ In particular, we did not investigate the financial implications of moving from a subscription to an Open Access publishing.

Economic impact pathways delineate the causal mechanisms and sequential processes through which Open Science practices generate economic value.

PathOS contributes to the empirical evidence base through systematic case study analysis across diverse contexts, offering new insights into economic pathways and their mechanisms. These methodological approaches help illuminate how Open Science practices generate economic value, though significant evidence gaps remain. Economic impact pathways delineate the causal mechanisms and sequential processes through which these practices operate.

Table 4 below summarises these findings (column B), with the intended effects (column A) presented for comparison.

Table 4. Comparison of intended economic impacts and summarised findings of impact

OS Mechanism	A. Intended economic impacts	B. Summary of our findings
<i>Access</i>	Increased access to research data, tools or results is intended to enhance the productivity of research activities, not only within academia, as discussed in Chapter 3, but also in industry. When researchers gain unlimited and cost-free access to prior scientific outputs, they avoid duplication and redundancies, thereby saving both time and financial resources. This streamlining effect generates system-wide efficiency and accelerates knowledge generation and dissemination cycles.	Open Science speeds knowledge creation and reduces the related efforts and costs. Easy and free access to scientific knowledge is linked to costs and time savings in research activities and, if additional facilitating factors occur (like additional investment in R&D), it may enhance innovation and ultimately, contribute to economic growth.
<i>Transparency</i>	Increased transparency of the research process is not only thought to increase the trust in and credibility of research among researchers, but also among the public and societal actors.	<i>No findings</i>
<i>Participation</i>	Increased participation is intended to make research more equitable, multidisciplinary and productive through the empowerment of a greater range of research actors to	When research outputs circulate openly through scientific communities and beyond, researchers can build cumulatively on existing knowledge foundations with greater speed and scope. This accessibility has an enablement effect, fostering novel

	increase the scope and efficiency of research activities.	interdisciplinary collaborations and cross-sector partnerships, potentially accelerating both fundamental discoveries and applied innovations.
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Building on Fell (2019), we identify two pathways to economic impact (Figure 8):

- An **Efficiency** pathway which operates through the immediate reduction of the costs of research processes and activities. The efficiency pathway manifests through more proximal, short-term economic effects where causal attribution to specific Open Science practices can be established with greater methodological confidence. These effects often materialise as quantifiable resource savings and productivity enhancements that can be directly measured within defined timeframes and organisational boundaries. It should be noted that this is the same pathway already identified and described under the academic impact section. However, here the effect is investigated under a purely economic angle and by considering also other affected actors beyond academia, in particular industrial users.
- An **Enablement** pathway, that is the catalytic role played by Open Science on innovation and growth opportunities: this more complex pathway operates by expanding the space for scientific advancement and cross-sectoral innovation and it is mainly leveraged by collaboration. Unlike the efficiency pathway, enablement effects typically emerge over extended time periods and manifest as higher-order economic impacts, including enhanced innovation capacity and wider economic growth. These effects demonstrate more contingent relationships to Open Science practices, often requiring complementary conditions and facilitating factors (such as strategic investments in research infrastructure, human capital development, innovation capacity among others) to fully materialise.

Economic Impacts of Open Science

Figure 8. Diagrammatic representation of the impact pathways for economic impact

The two pathways (Figure 8) differ not only in their temporal scope but also in the nature of the changes they represent. The **efficiency pathway** pertains to doing the same research activities more effectively or more rapidly, essentially reflecting incremental improvements. These are tasks that could be accomplished without Open Science but are executed more efficiently due to Open Access to data, tools, and findings. In contrast, the **enablement pathway** is associated with more transformative change, wherein Open Science practices make possible new forms of research that would not otherwise be feasible. This includes enhanced collaboration between academia and industry, greater interdisciplinarity, and the generation of novel research questions or approaches that emerge specifically because of increased openness and accessibility.

The distinction between the two pathways is not always clear-cut; rather, they are conceptually interlinked. Gains achieved through the efficiency pathway, such as reductions in cost and time, can lay the groundwork for broader, long-term impacts. Enhanced research productivity, driven by these efficiencies, may in turn accelerate innovation, thereby catalysing the enablement pathway.

This dual-pathway framework, further specified for specific Open Science practices, provides a structured approach for analysing how different Open Science interventions propagate through research ecosystems to generate economic impacts, while acknowledging the differing time periods, attribution challenges, and contextual dependencies associated with each pathway. A key insight from the project is the importance of causal mechanisms. The identified economic effects are not automatic; they depend on enabling conditions and facilitating factors. Understanding these pathways and the underlying conditions is critical for the understanding and measuring of the economic impacts of Open Science and for informing policies that maximize societal and economic returns.

In the following sections, we describe in further detail the collected PathOS findings regarding economic impact.

5.2. Efficiency pathway

Empirical evidence from the literature is overall limited to few papers (Tsipouri et al. 2025). Among them however, **efficiency gains** represent the most documented outcome (**strong evidence**) across Open Science practices, primarily manifested through reduced time and costs associated with research output access and reuse. Efficiency gains correspond to the efficiency pathway described above.

Studies of Open/FAIR Data services consistently demonstrate substantial efficiency benefits provided by large data sharing platforms. Although data creation, curation, deposition and data

retrieval are costly activities and require time and skills, user-reported value often exceed these costs by factors of four to twelve, as documented in multiple analyses of European and British data repositories (Beagrie and Houghton 2012; 2013a; 2013b; 2014; 2021). Although the evidence available for these cases is strong, it is limited to specific initiatives willing to justify their value to their funding agencies. Systematic controlled comparisons are not feasible in such cases since these initiatives are rather unique, and a suitable alternative cannot be found.

Similar efficiency patterns emerge for Open Access publication, where more **moderate evidence** is available. Empirical research based on survey data indicates that without access to academic publications, SMEs in Denmark would have taken an extra 2.2 years to develop certain innovations (Houghton et al. 2011). Impact is not limited to the industry however: Look and Marsh, (2012) estimated £ 28.6 million (corresponding to EUR 33 million in nominal terms) in direct cost savings for the UK public sector attributable to Open Access through both Green and Gold routes. Finally, research productivity during the COVID-19 pandemic was estimated to have increased by about 1.2% each day in the period of April 2020–June 2021 as compared to other research fields thanks to the peculiar evolution of science production in that period facilitated by, among other factors, Open Access publication (Coccia 2021).

Limited evidence is available about Open-Source Software, with only four studies reporting on selected specific initiatives. Evidence points to a contribution of Open-Source Software to efficiency through reduced development costs and accelerated time-to-market, particularly benefiting organizations with appropriate absorptive capacities. One study based on a specific case of drug discovery proved that the adoption of Open Methods, i.e. a collaborative scientific research environment without retaining IP rights or exclusive access to findings, produced significant timesaving.

As indicated in the **PathOS Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook** (Apartis et al. 2024) and illustrated by the literature, [Cost savings](#) is the key indicator for measuring efficiency gains. The saved costs can be related to different aspect of scientific production, but typically they are associated with reduced time spent on given activities (e.g., working hours), or avoided storage and access costs. The Handbook suggests a comprehensive list of potential savings: labour cost savings, transaction cost savings, storage cost savings. Three approaches are identified in the Handbook for their quantification. The avoided cost method calculates savings by determining what users would have paid for equivalent closed-access resources. The stated preference approach employs Contingent Valuation surveys or Choice Experiments to elicit users' willingness-to-pay for Open Science resources when market prices are unavailable or inadequate, requiring case-specific primary data collection. Finally, the Long Run Marginal Cost method evaluates Open Science resources based on the counterfactual expense of independently producing equivalent outputs, focusing exclusively on direct production costs to

prevent double-counting with other benefit categories. The evidence from the literature shows that the most widespread approach is Contingent Valuation survey.

Building on the evidence from the literature and in line with the Handbook (Apartis et al. 2024), two PathOS case studies focused on efficiency gains: UniProt and RCAAP. **The CBA case study on ELIXIR's UniProt** (Catalano et al. 2025c), a curated protein sequence database, demonstrates that expert biocuration and free access generate significant net economic benefits, yielding annual benefits per user ranging from €3,513 to €5,475 (Catalano et al. 2025c). Labour cost savings are especially high among private sector users, indicating substantial R&D workflow efficiencies.

The PathOS CBA framework enabled systematic assessment despite UniProt's uniqueness, employing multiple data sources including user surveys, focus groups, usage analytics, and cost analysis to understand impact mechanisms and user diversity. The analysis systematically evaluated alternative valuation methods (avoided costs, contingent valuation) before determining that monetizing time savings was most appropriate for UniProt's context. A key finding is that **significant time savings stem from data integration and manual annotation rather than openness alone**, highlighting that infrastructure quality and curation are decisive factors in generating economic value. The study's novelty also lies in focusing on one specific digital resource rather than institutional service portfolios, enabling more precise attribution of economic value.

The **RCAAP CBA** case study (Catalano et al. 2025b) provides a complementary perspective, examining Portugal's national network of institutional repositories, which aggregates multiple repositories through a single portal to enhance visibility and accessibility of Portuguese research outputs. The CBA demonstrates that, despite significant personnel costs (>70% of expenses) and user training investments, benefits exceed costs by approximately 33%, with this ratio likely underestimated due to conservative assumptions (Catalano et al. 2025b).

The analysis employed a conservative counterfactual comparing RCAAP's integrated approach against uncoordinated individual repositories rather than a closed system. The primary quantifiable benefits derived from institutional cost savings through **resource pooling and economies of scale, with labour cost savings representing the most substantial component**. The study revealed a distinctive pattern where significant costs are distributed at the institutional level rather than centralized operations, demonstrating how coordinated infrastructure generates system-wide efficiencies.

5.3. Enablement Pathway

Pathway to innovation

Innovation enhancement, conceptualised as part of the enablement pathway, constitutes the second major impact category. Open/FAIR Data demonstrates the most documented contribution to innovation enhancement (**moderate evidence**). Studies particularly in genomics and pharmaceuticals confirm that reduced access barriers stimulate downstream research and product development (Arshad et al. 2016; Giovani 2017) while, on contrary, IP protections have a negative impact on innovation (Williams 2013). Open Access publications show increased patent citations, suggesting greater integration of scientific outputs in innovation processes. Here the **evidence is strong** (using counterfactual and patent data citations) though limited to two studies (Bryan and Ozcan 2021; Jahn et al. 2022). Similarly, Open-Source Software supports innovation in startups and emerging technology sectors by lowering development barriers and facilitating collaborative approaches (Conti et al. 2021; European Commission et al. 2021).

In the **PathOS Indicator Handbook**, the indicator (Arshad et al. 2016; Giovani 2017) aims to capture the extent to which Open Science triggers innovation in industry and the scientific community in a broad sense, spanning beyond the narrow proxy of patents. It indeed considers both the development and enhancement of products, services, technologies, the filing of patents and the launch of new companies. Here, five metrics are proposed: 1) new products and services developed by using Open Science input, 2) new technologies developed by using Open Science input, 3) start-ups and spin-offs founded based on Open Science technologies, 4) patents filed citing Open Science inputs, and 5) average increase in companies' patent portfolio value thanks to the patent filed using Open Science resources. Against this wide perspective, empirical evidence considered in the scoping review mostly concentrates on patent-related metrics. Another relevant indicator identified in the **Handbook** and related to the innovation processes is the one related to [Science-industry collaboration](#). It captures the collaborative efforts between academia and industry and focuses on the exchange of knowledge and resources that facilitate the development of new technologies, processes, or products, thereby advancing scientific understanding and commercial applications. Notable metrics are co-patenting or co-publications.

Patent citations provide a key pathway for Open Science to drive innovation across multiple PathOS case studies. The **Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence** study found that Green OA publications show modest increases in patent citations, indicating enhanced knowledge transfer to practical applications. Similarly, the **Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications** case study revealed that artifact reuse is causally linked to moderate increases

in patent citations, particularly when research was high quality, widely visible, and published early in the pandemic. These findings suggest that open sharing facilitates the translation of research into technological innovation.

Science-industry collaboration represents another major enablement mechanism consistently observed across PathOS case studies. The **Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence** case demonstrated higher science-industry collaboration rates for Green OA publications in AI-for-Climate research compared to closed access. The **Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications** case found that artifact reuse strengthens links to science-industry collaboration, driving technological innovation and industrial uptake. The **ELIXIR's Bioinformatics Resources** case study demonstrates how open bioinformatics resources foster science-industry collaborations that drive economic growth, digital skills development, and labor market benefits. Lastly, The **Portuguese Repository Infrastructure RCAAP** case study provides additional evidence of enhanced collaboration intensity among organisations of different activity sectors. The consistency of this collaboration enhancement across such diverse contexts - crisis response, emerging research areas, and established infrastructure - suggests that strengthening science-industry links is a fundamental mechanism through which Open Science creates economic value.

Economic sector utilization patterns reveal differential value creation across different parts of the economy. The **French Open Access Infrastructure** case study provides quantitative evidence that for economic sectors beyond education, Open Science publications are accessed 3.5% more frequently than closed publications. Specific sectors show even greater benefits: public administration (8%) and professional activities (9%), indicating that economic value varies significantly by sector type and suggesting targeted policy approaches could maximize returns.

These enablement pathway findings emerge from methodologically sophisticated approaches including AI-driven analysis, mixed-methods integration, systematic use of access logs, focus groups, and systematic attention to causal identification challenges. However, as is typical for empirical studies, perfect experimental control over unobservable factors was not achieved. Factors such as institutional reputation, author prestige, research sensitivity, or disciplinary norms may contribute to observed effects. These limitations are explicitly acknowledged across all case studies.

As pointed out in the Handbook, Cost savings are closely connected to the metrics of "Innovation Output". The underlying rationale is that time and financial savings can be reinvested into R&D activities, which, over time, may lead to enhanced R&D productivity and greater innovation outcomes.

With the intention to investigate the impact pathway beyond immediate cost savings and related to innovation enhancement, the **CBA case study of ELIXIR'S UniProt** included a further

investigation relying on a citation and patent analysis. This analysis shows that, beyond short-term time and cost savings, UniProt contributes meaningfully to scientific progress and innovation, as evidenced by its widespread citation in academic literature and patent filings, and its role in fostering academic-industry collaborations and entrepreneurial activities. Publications and patents analysis shows the contribution that research enabled by UniProt had on innovation triggered by the new knowledge flow (Catalano et al. 2025c). While relevant to reconstruct the enablement pathway, this evidence does not allow a causal claim between UniProt and the observed innovation. Although linked to the use of UniProt, their materialisation also depends on additional user effort and resources.

From **the RCAAP CBA case study** evidence of innovation enhancement is weaker. While the analysis provides compelling evidence for short-term efficiency benefits, longer-term impacts on research acceleration and knowledge diffusion, though potentially significant, remain difficult to quantify due to attribution challenges and alternative access pathways (Catalano et al. 2025b).

The PathOS CBA framework represents a methodological advance in systematically evaluating innovation pathways from specific Open Science resources, moving beyond institutional-level assessments to resource-specific impact attribution.

Pathway to economic growth

A third potential impact of Open Science, **economic growth**, still part of the enablement pathway, remains more speculative, with limited evidence predominantly derived from macroeconomic modelling and simulation rather than empirical observation with causal attribution. While growth models suggest that modest increases in openness could generate significant economic returns, particularly for Open Access (Houghton and Sheehan 2006; 2009) and Open/FAIR Data initiatives (Tripp and Grueber 2011; Beagrie and Houghton 2021; Sullivan et al. 2017), these estimates rely on assumptions that are challenging to validate empirically and face substantial attribution difficulties (**limited evidence**).

Existing literature has in fact limited ability to disentangle Open Science effects from confounding factors such as research excellence or funding availability. Especially for more indirect effects, Open Science practices are claimed to be contributors to economic impact, i.e. holding a supporting role among other factors. The Human Genome Project exemplifies the challenge in isolating Open Science impacts from other factors: while economic models suggest (**limited evidence**) it generated \$796 billion in economic activity against a \$3.8 billion federal investment (equivalent to approximately EUR 684 billion and EUR 3.2 billion in nominal terms, respectively), critics question whether these impressive returns can be directly attributed to

Open Data practices or instead reflect parallel private and public investments in genomics (Wadman 2013).

The key indicator identified in the **PathOS Indicator Handbook** related to economic growth is the [Economic growth of companies](#). It stresses however that direct effects of Open Science on the economic growth of companies are difficult to capture and to isolate because little data is readily available about company-level benefits from or adoption of Open Science practices. Another interesting indicator is the one related to [Socially relevant products and services](#), addressing the adoption and integration of Open Science inputs for advancements in medical treatments, drugs, sustainable agricultural practices, and new renewable energy technologies that contribute to societal well-being. The Handbook however acknowledges the challenges in finding appropriate metrics to solidly measure this impact. The last indicator of relevance identified by the Handbook is [Labour market impact of Open Science](#) which refers to effects of Open Science on the skills and competences of researchers and research support staff. Qualitative changes can be identified by investigating job descriptions and the types of skills and competences which they require.

The literature shows that the economic benefits of Open Science are not uniform across sectors. Biomedical and bioindustry is the most studied discipline, probably for the longstanding practice of sharing data, science-industry collaboration, strong regulatory framework and the relevance to global health.

5.4. Lessons learned

The transition to Open Science is increasingly seen not only as a normative shift in scholarly communication but also as a strategic enabler of economic efficiency, innovation, and socio-economic development. While the policy case for Open Science is often built on expectations of impact, the empirical evidence base remains fragmented, particularly with respect to economic effects. Key lessons learned are the following:

- **Fragmented and methodologically limited evidence base:** the empirical literature remains fragmented, with many studies relying on case studies and self-reported data subject to bias. Most critically, studies lack robust counterfactual analysis, making it difficult to disentangle Open Science effects from other variables such as research excellence or funding levels. While existing evidence suggests plausible pathways, it rarely provides definitive proof.
- **Causal attribution remains challenging:** Disentangling the effects of Open Science from other variables, such as research excellence, funding levels, and interdisciplinarity, remains difficult. Economic impacts are often mediated and indirect, as illustrated by examples like the Human Genome Project.

- **Contributory more than causal:** the relationship between Open Science practices and long-term economic outcomes is better understood as contributory rather than directly causal, due to the complexity of innovation systems, the fact that they are often realised in the medium or long term and the interplay of multiple influencing factors.
- **Cost Benefit Analysis as a structured yet resource-intensive methodology:** Cost Benefit Analysis offers a structured framework for evaluating the costs and benefits of Open Science initiatives, encouraging a more systematic assessment mindset. However, its effective application requires specialised expertise and robust data monitoring systems. Key challenges include clearly defining the contributions of collaborative partners, establishing credible “what-if” scenarios to estimate value, and addressing the difficulty of tracking open resource usage, which often results in conservative impact estimates.
- **Limited comparative evidence:** much of the (limited) literature examines Open Science economic benefits without systematically comparing these outcomes to non-Open Science alternatives, creating uncertainty about the magnitude and attribution of observed effects.
- **Methodological innovation enables progress despite challenges:** PathOS demonstrates that advancing Open Science evaluation requires innovative approaches combining AI-driven analysis, mixed-methods integration, and systematic attention to causal identification. While perfect causal attribution remains elusive, these methodological advances enable more robust evidence generation than traditional approaches.

6. Discussion and conclusion

PathOS was designed as an iterative project, with a synthesis stage designed to bring all conceptual and empirical findings from the project together in service of the development of evidence-based Key Impact Pathways for Open Science. To this end, we have identified three Key Impact Pathways. These are driven by Open Science interventions that enable (1) **access** to scientific and scholarly outputs; (2) **transparency** of the scientific and scholarly process; and (3) **participation** of diverse actors in the scientific and scholarly process (Table 5).

Table 5. Key impact pathways for Open Science

	Academic Impacts	Societal Impacts	Economic Impacts
Access	Open Science speeds knowledge sharing and reduces redundant efforts and costs. Access to scientific knowledge seems to have positive effects (measured in terms of citations and reuse) upon the use of that knowledge though effects vary by access pathway (repository vs. journal-based) and depend on research quality and infrastructure design.	Open Science enables societal actors to access and reuse research outputs, which democratises scientific knowledge and drives societal impacts including empowerment of people and communities, benefits to the environment and climate, and to health and safety. When industrial actors reuse research outputs, societally relevant innovations may be produced though PathOS found that access and reuse do not automatically translate to societal impact, particularly in clinical contexts.	Open Science enables industrial actors to access and reuse research outputs, which fosters efficiency in industrial innovation and enables the development of new skills and research areas within industry. Together, these outcomes contribute to impacts including enhanced innovation, economic growth, and labour market growth.
Transparency	Open Science encourages transparency and accountability, although ethical risks	<i>No findings</i>	<i>No findings</i>

	<p>remain. Open Science promotes reproducibility, but practical outcomes depend on effective implementation. Increased transparency shows some evidence of increasing quality of knowledge, which may in turn have effects upon use (given increased trust).</p>		
<p>Participation</p>	<p>Open Science facilitates interdisciplinary and cross-sector collaborations, though impacts vary with context. Increased participation fosters new methods of data collection (especially via Citizen Science) and the wider accessibility and reuse, underpinning interdisciplinarity and collaboration; however, persisting structural inequalities may shape possibilities for participation in unexpected ways, meaning that equity</p>	<p>Participatory research approaches, whether academically- or community-driven, democratise research, foster social ties and cohesion among participants and communities, enable reuse of research outputs by societal actors, drive increases in knowledge and awareness among participants and communities, foster behavioural change, and enable trust between stakeholders. Together, these outcomes lead to positive impacts on equity and empowerment, on the environment and</p>	<p>When research outputs circulate openly through scientific communities and beyond, researchers can build cumulatively on existing knowledge foundations with greater speed and scope. This accessibility has an enablement effect, fostering novel interdisciplinary collaborations and cross-sector partnerships, potentially accelerating both fundamental discoveries and applied innovations.</p>

	must be closely monitored.	climate, and in health and safety.	
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The synthesised findings from our scoping reviews (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024; Klebel et al. 2025; Tsipouri et al. 2025), case studies (Stavropoulos et al. 2025a) and CBA (Catalano et al. 2025a) show that these KIPs drive **academic impacts** in quality, efficiency and productivity, and equity, diversity and inclusion; **societal impacts** in equity and empowerment, climate and environment, and health and safety; and **economic impacts** in innovation and economic growth. Academic impacts achieved by providing access to outputs are driven by outcomes in citations and readership, and reuse, while participation of actors drives collaboration as an outcome, leading to impacts. Societal impacts are driven primarily by participation of societal actors, but access to outputs also leads to reuse as an outcome that drives impact. Economic impacts are driven by access to outputs, with cost and time savings as key outcomes that drive impact. In Chapter 7, we build on these findings to present recommendations for increasing impact from Open Science.

6.1. Intersecting pathways from access

Our synthesis shows that academic, societal, and economic impacts may intersect and reinforce each other through the access, transparency, and participation pathways, though these relationships are not automatic and depend on contextual factors and implementation approaches. This finding challenges assumptions in much of the existing literature, which tends to study impacts in isolation rather than examining their interconnections. While different types of impacts can occur independently, PathOS case studies demonstrate that academic benefits can connect to both economic and societal outcomes when enabling conditions are present. The apparent rarity of such intersecting pathways in previous research may reflect methodological limitations and disciplinary silos rather than their actual infrequency. There are a handful of exceptions indicated by the evidence.

As demonstrated in Figure 9, the cost impact of Gold OA publishing has both positive and negative equity impact. While the cost of accessing publications is removed by this Open Science intervention, authors must pay to publish. Therefore, there may be a positive equity impact of removing financial barriers to accessing publications, but a negative equity impact of requiring authors to pay to publish. These equity impacts may occur both in the academic (publication and readership) (see Chapter 3) and societal realms (readership) (see Chapter 4).

Figure 9. Gold Open Access impact pathway

Similarly, our case study focused on the RCAAP publication repository in Portugal (Figure 10) found that a combination of economic and academic outcomes, some intersecting, may lead to the development of new solutions in response to societal challenges (societal impact) (Stavropoulos et al. 2025aa).

Figure 10. RCAAP impact pathway

Similarly, our ELIXIR case study focused on the UniProt database (a curated, open outputs repository) (Figure 11) found that short-term academic and economic outcomes are leading to long-term outcomes in both realms. These, in turn, lead to academic and economic impact that both lead to downstream societal impact in the form of new solutions that respond to societal challenges (Stavropoulos et al. 2025a).

Figure 11. ELIXIR UniProt impact pathway

6.2. Intersecting pathways from participation

Evidence derived from our scoping reviews of academic (Klebel et al. 2025) and societal impact (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024) also suggests a relationship between the participation of societal actors via Citizen Science, which can increase the scale and efficiency of data collection and generate data that is used by societal actors to monitor and manage natural resources. Additionally, when Open Science practices diversify participation in research (academic and societal), novel solutions may be identified for responding to societal challenges (societal impact).

6.3. Lessons learned

Limited evidence

Our analysis reveals large gaps in the evidence. Firstly, studies on longer-term impacts are scarce in comparison to studies related to uptake. Large-scale monitoring efforts (EC's Open Science Monitor (European Commission 2019) and various national monitors (Bracco 2022; Barbers et al. 2022; Bracco et al. 2022)) also focus predominantly on the latter, usually via monitoring of numbers of outputs (Open Access publications, datasets, etc). If monitoring and

evaluation efforts continue to focus primarily on whether researchers are implementing Open Science practices, rather than if this uptake is leading to the real-world changes they are assumed to have, then policy will continue to be guided by intuition and not evidence. This is especially important since it is now widely recognised that making outputs open does not ensure the mobilisation of that knowledge. Enabling capacities (cf. absorptive capacity) heavily shape the possibilities for exploitation, and those capacities (in terms of enabling infrastructures and local knowledge) are far from evenly distributed. Moreover, too narrow a focus on outputs limits recognition of broader processes and other aspects of behavioural additionality (Aschhoff et al. 2006). Greater clarity on the relationship between the overall aims of the Open Science programme and its expression via values will enable improved monitoring.

We can also see uneven evidence across the research lifecycle and over-emphasis on certain Open Science practices and outcomes. Impact assessments tend to cluster around Open Access publication, Citizen Science and data sharing, with limited evaluation of upstream practices (e.g., Open Methods, Evaluation) or some downstream outcomes like reuse, reproducibility, collaboration, and societal and economic impacts. Our synthesis of the evidence surrounding academic impact reveals an overemphasis on citation advantage over other possible outcomes and impacts, like diversity of readership. It also reveals a lack of attention to the role of quality and data management and curation practices in enabling the reuse of open outputs. We also find a lack of attention to how Open Science practices affect the efficiency of the research process, and their impact on equity (positive and negative) (Klebel et al. 2025). Similarly, our synthesis of the evidence surrounding societal impact raises many unanswered questions. We have extremely limited evidence of societal impact from Open/FAIR Data and Open Code/Software/and Tools. This evidence indicates a positive societal impact but is too limited in scope and scale to make any conclusion. Questions remain as to whether Open Access publications lead to societal impact, since studies to date have analysed reach and engagement, rather than use and impact. So far, no attention has been paid to the societal impact of transparency of the research process. Finally, we lack any evidence of societal impact in relation to dynamics of power and inequality, or societal challenges beyond environment/climate and health (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024). And, as noted previously, there is limited evidence of Open Science's economic impact. The evidence that we identified and produced focuses on access to research outputs and indicates positive impact on innovation and economic growth but is too limited in scope and scale to draw strong conclusions (Tsipouri et al. 2025).

These limitations in evidence create gaps in understanding how and when openness generates value. This is perhaps driven in part by a "streetlight effect" of measuring what is easy to measure. This suggestion is supported by proliferation of studies of citation impact or individual case reports of Citizen Science initiatives from those involved in such projects. This may suggest a misalignment between monitoring and evaluation indicators and stakeholders' values and

aims. Current monitoring frameworks often focus on easily measurable outputs, such as publications, datasets, and code, while overlooking the relational dynamics through which real impact often occurs. This limits the relevance of findings for real-world decision-making, even when evaluations are well-executed. Policy influence, societal uptake, and behavioural change frequently emerge from collaboration, engagement, and long-term trust-building. These dimensions are harder to quantify, but crucial to assess.

In addition, our findings indicate something of a skew towards positive results suggestive of potential publication bias. The available literature may reflect broader structural incentives in academic publishing that favor positive findings over null or negative results. This pattern is well-documented across many research domains and may also affect Open Science evaluation studies, where inconclusive or negative findings could be underrepresented in the published record. If this is the case, it would lead to an incomplete picture of real effects.

We suggest that the unevenness of this evidence-base is related to a lack of strategic direction in impact evaluation, and hence an overreliance on bottom-up efforts. Open Science impact research often lacks coordinated programmes and is driven by individual researchers, creating scattered coverage. Policymakers or funders could set (and fund) priorities for investigation. Coordination would not require centralisation, thematic or domain-based frameworks could offer a shared spine while supporting bottom-up diversity.

In addition, lack of funding for such studies may exacerbate “streetlight effects” confining the scope, quality, and replication of Open Science evaluations. Furthermore, greater strategic efforts and evaluation of impact (as opposed to uptake) will enable greater reflexive learning from purposive evaluation efforts that seek not just to keep investments accountable or enable benchmarking, but also informing future strategy regarding what is working, to which ends, in specific different contexts. We build on these conclusions by offering recommendations for improving the evidence base for impact evaluation in Chapter 7.

Methodological issues

Our synthesis of the evidence also illuminates problems *per se* in evaluation in this area and more specific issues regarding methods currently deployed. These can be categorised as temporal issues, causal issues, diversity issues, and study design and reporting issues.

TEMPORAL ISSUES

The Open Science landscape evolves rapidly, with new infrastructures, mandates, and practices emerging continuously. Traditional evaluation methods may lag due to this evolving technological and practical landscape, and by the time a metric becomes standardised, the target practice may have changed. This challenges long-term planning and the relevance of

historical evaluations. In a similar vein, there is typically a temporal disconnect between implementation and evaluation. Many Open Science evaluations begin well after practices are adopted, missing early-stage insights that could inform scale-up, sustainability, or redesign. As a result, we often learn about outcomes but not about the conditions that enabled (or hindered) success. Finally, impacts typically emerge over the long-term. Different Open Science interventions may have different impact timelines. Some, like preprints, may have fast effects, while others, like data reuse, take years. Short evaluation windows will not be able to capture long-term changes.

CAUSAL ISSUES

Our scoping of the literature (Cole, Kormann, et al. 2024; Klebel et al. 2025; Tsipouri et al. 2025) and the development of the PathOS conceptual framework (Dekker et al. 2023) identified causality as a key issue that needs to be established in Open Science impact assessment. However, linking openness to actual impacts is challenging; often no counterfactuals are established or weak design in controlling for confounders or colliders is used (Klebel and Traag 2025). Without robust methods (e.g., controlled comparisons, longitudinal data), claims of impact are often speculative at best. Lack of reporting standards, common vocabularies, difference between the effect of a certain Open Science practice on impact (whether Open Access leads to more diverse citations compared to closed access) and the impact of the practice (whether citations in Open Access articles are diverse) are underappreciated. A lack of longitudinal data is also an issue here, often making it challenging to distinguish correlation from causation. Therefore, we conclude that establishing causal links between Open Science practices and impacts remains a major methodological gap.

DIVERSITY ISSUES

Open Science interventions are diverse, they take place at differing levels, and impacts are diverse and need to be captured in differing ways. In addition, it cannot be expected that all data can be standardised (no one size fits all indicators for the diverse KPIs or impacts). The context for this diversified landscape is disciplinary and institutional diversity. Different fields, institutions and geographic regions have varying norms, possibilities for implementation, and rates of Open Science adoption, often hinging on epistemic difference and the appropriateness of Open Science practices given this (Cole, Ulpts, Bochynska, Kormann, Good, Leitner, et al. 2024), available resources for implementation (Ross-Hellauer, Reichmann, et al. 2022) and varying incentives. Therefore, uniform metrics, without contextual understanding and interpretation, might distort findings or exclude relevant measures of impact. Standardised metrics and expectations also pose the threat of epistemic marginalisation and penalty for those fields or research areas where Open Science is not a good fit (Cole, Ulpts, Bochynska, Kormann, Good, Leitner, et al. 2024) or who are under-resourced for implementation (Ross-

Hellauer, Reichmann, et al. 2022). On the other hand, indicators themselves are also diverse and hard to align. Standard metrics like citations, and downloads do not capture some qualities, and newly emerging measures often lack broad acceptance, consistent use or knowledge of how to normalise them for the meta research field.

STUDY DESIGN AND REPORTING ISSUES

Our synthesised findings show that impact is often difficult to quantify (as compared to uptake), and therefore qualitative or mixed-method approaches may be more appropriate for assessing impacts that emerge over the long-term. However, when such approaches are taken, often in the form of case studies, the ability to generalise based on findings or to capture broad based effects may be lost. We see this in the evidence base, with many impact analyses stemming from local, initiative-driven case studies—often with publication biases and context-bound results. How can the meta research community compare findings across settings or draw broader conclusions? As Louise Bezuidenhout and colleagues put it, “For [case studies] to be more than proof of activity, they need to be responsibly curated and searchable” (Bezuidenhout et al. 2024), which suggests a need for new “FAIR data standards and controlled vocabularies” to enable cross-case analysis (Bezuidenhout et al. 2024).

On the data side, we see problems with fragmentation and inconsistent reporting. Repositories, funders, and institutions track usage in disparate ways, complicating attempts to do cross-study comparisons or meta-analyses of Open Science impacts. Part of the problem here is an underdeveloped data infrastructure. A lack of standards for tracking data and code reuse, inconsistent metadata, and ad hoc reporting all hamper efforts to compare and aggregate Open Science impact across contexts.

Finally, as Open Science evaluation increasingly engages with large and unstructured data sources (from publications to policy documents), computational methods, including machine learning, offer powerful ways to map impact across the research lifecycle. These tools can help identify how innovations or topics evolve under different names, formats, or domains. However, while technically promising, these approaches are not yet widely standardised or validated for routine use in policy or monitoring contexts. Their results often face trust and interpretability barriers, especially outside data science communities.

Conceptual issues

“Start with what you value” is the first step of the SCOPE Framework for Research Evaluation (REF). Yet, pinning down the values of Open Science is not simple. As a whole, Open Science is typified by a diversity of practices and aims and is argued to be “a constellation of communities, rather than a single, homogeneous one” (Field, p. 149). “Different stakeholders hold disparate

understandings of Open Science, often associated with different conceptual models and interests about what science is and aims to accomplish” (Rafols et al. 2024). Despite consensus-building initiatives like the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO 2021b), different stakeholders from different communities may still take contradictory views on its core values (and hence overall aims). The UNESCO recommendation, for example, did not foreground efficiency despite this being a core component of earlier definitions (see Annex A). While individual initiatives can helpfully be guided to formulate their own reflection on values, if different stakeholders define “open” differently, this complicates any broader unified assessment. What is more, if key values and their prioritisation are left unclear at the beginning, this has arguably limited the extent to which broader initiatives have been based on a rigorous “theory of change”. Rather, we might suggest, Open Science has been based on a folk theory of change. This has downstream implications for evaluation as lack of clarity about the scope and aim of Open Science translates into the impossibility or inconsistency of reconstructing a clear theory of change, which is the first step of a solid assessment exercise. Open Science’s decentralised nature makes top-down theories of change difficult, but this doesn’t mean pathway thinking is impossible. Without a theory of change, indicators can become disconnected from goals, which is risky at the policy level. Without such a sound starting causal picture, we can only reach poor understanding of interaction effects and impacts. In addition, Open Science often interacts with broader research improvements (like RRI, research integrity, research assessment reform, changes in funding landscape), so isolating the effect of “openness” from other changes is difficult.

Therefore, in addition to the issues raised above that hamper understanding of Open Science impact and assessing it, we note the need for governments, organisations, and institutions to establish clarity on what the aims of Open Science are in their context, before they begin collecting data and design impact evaluation strategies. These need not be necessarily uniform, because contextual diversity should shape these, but where they can align, they will enable bigger-picture, overarching impact assessment.

In what follows, Chapter 7, we present evidence-based, co-designed recommendations (by both internal project stakeholders and external ones from the broader Open Science and meta research communities). These recommendations respond to the issues raised in this chapter, as well as broadly within the findings of this report, and offer guidance on increasing Open Science impact, improving the impact evidence base, and improving methods of impact assessment.

7. Recommendations

Building on the synthesis findings presented in this report, and in direct response to the issues described in Chapter 6, PathOS has prepared the following evidence-based, collaboratively designed recommendations to increase the impact of Open Science and improve how we study and understand it. These recommendations were iteratively prepared through inter-consortium workshops and discussions, and through external stakeholder validation (through in-person presentation and discussion and in-document collaboration). These recommendations are designed to support the work of researchers, institutions, funders, policymakers and monitoring groups.

In what follows, we present recommendations in three categories: 1) improving methods of impact assessment; 2) improving the evidence-base; and 3) increasing Open Science impact.

Table 6. Overview of PathOS recommendations

Category	Number	Recommendation Title
Methods	R1.1	Update Open Science impact indicators and metrics on a regular review cycle to account for evolving technologies and practices
	R1.2	Strategically design impact evaluation plans across all phases of implementation
	R1.3	Choose study designs and methods with impact pathway dynamics in mind
	R1.4	Support development and implementation of reporting guidelines for impact studies
	R1.5	Support Open Research infrastructures for data relevant to impact assessment
	R1.6	Support evaluation approaches that address causality and long-term impact
Evidence	R2.1	Study more Open Science interventions, outcomes and impacts and promote a diversity of evidence
	R2.2	Move focus in investigations from uptake to impact
	R2.3	Explicitly document negative results, not only successes
	R2.4	Stakeholders in the Open Science reform movement should take the initiative to define key evidence gaps from their standpoints
	R2.5	Increase resources and support for impact studies
	R2.6	Establish PathOS 2.0: A systematic Open Science Impact research initiative
Impact	R3.1	Increase support for the diversification of participation in scientific research
	R3.2	Increase support for equitable sharing of quality open outputs
	R3.3	Attend to issues of equity and capacity in reuse

	R3.4	Expand efforts to increase transparency based on evidence
	R3.5	Balance the need for proprietary resources with the aims of openness

7.1. Improve methods for impact assessment

PathOS found that methods and study designs for impact assessment are often less than optimal due to a variety of issues, including those related to temporality, diversity, and causality. Here, we present recommendations designed to respond to these issues. Critical to improving Open Science assessment practices will be the inclusion of a diversity of stakeholders in identifying impact questions, identifying and capturing relevant high-quality data, and designing impact assessments that are appropriate to diverse contexts.

R1.1 Update Open Science impact indicators and metrics on a regular review cycle to account for evolving technologies and practices

Open Science interventions and their impacts exist in a rapidly evolving technological landscape, especially with the growth in AI and its integration into research workflows and user engagement. Just as these dynamics evolve, so too should how we measure and study Open Science impact. In this process, all relevant stakeholders should be included and unintended consequences should be checked rigorously. Focus should be put on the important questions at hand (see also R2.3), only rolling out indicators with a strong theoretical foundation. Updates need to be balanced with providing stable indicators to show change over time and with allowing time for trust and uptake of indicators to develop, not leaving any groups behind. To this end, the [PathOS Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook](#) has been designed as a living document that encourages ongoing community contributions, to revising existing indicators or adding new ones, beyond the life of the project. When defining indicators in the future, care should be taken not to create wrong incentives. Otherwise, Open Science bears the risk of only becoming a compliance exercise.

R1.2 Strategically design impact evaluation plans across all phases of implementation

Assessment data can best be gathered with forethought and intention, rather than in hindsight, and are of great value *before* an intervention is implemented, to have a baseline for comparison.

Stakeholders should have an idea of what their impact aims are, and which data should be gathered in order to evaluate its impact. For significant Open Science interventions, adopting CBA frameworks from the outset enables systematic economic evaluation and requires specific data collection on implementation costs, usage patterns, time savings, and quantifiable benefits that may not be captured in standard impact assessments. Resources should be allocated from the beginning to do so, and data should be gathered at a programme rather than an individual level to not add more administrative burden to researchers.

Additionally, most of what we know about Open Science impact is based on proxy measures of engagement or uptake. To truly study impact, we need methods and study designs oriented toward long-term tracking of Open Science interventions, their outcomes, and long-term impacts. Assessment data from all phases of implementation, especially before and after a longer follow-up allows the most thorough investigation of the impact of Open Science interventions.

When creating new Open Science initiatives, they should be designed with impact and its evaluation in mind. Doing so allows for the creation of an impact framework and KPIs at the design stage. Then, one can run ex-ante to assess expectations; regularly update KPIs to monitor performance; and systematically perform evaluations at set periods to assess long-term impact. See "[Designing a Research Infrastructure with Impact in Mind](#)" for specific guidance on this approach.

R1.3 Choose study designs and methods with impact pathway dynamics in mind

Much of the evidence base of Open Science impact fails to attend to the question of causality when looking to establish the effect of an intervention on an outcome. We recommend taking greater care in the methods and design of impact studies by attending to causality, laying bare assumptions about impact pathway dynamics, and with attention to various factors that might influence an outcome. Otherwise, even greater care needs to be taken when interpreting findings.

Because impact studies require a long-term view, and often, interaction with users to establish pathway dynamics, we recommend employing mixed methods and/or qualitative approaches to answer questions that cannot be answered by quantitative or computational methods. Indeed, qualitative methods may be best able to "identify underlying mechanisms and distinguishing policy influences from other factors...to establish causality" (Haddad and Bergek 2023). Additionally, interdisciplinary meta research is promising here, for its ability to combine qualitative insights, bibliometrics, policy analysis, and increasingly, computational tools. Yet

meaningful integration across these domains remains rare, often due to siloed data, incompatible assumptions, or lack of shared vocabulary. These issues must be addressed to advance the study of Open Science impact.

While individual case studies have value in closely examining the dynamics of particular interventions in specific contexts, understanding broader patterns of impact requires a higher-level view. We recommend independent investigations across initiatives and cross-case comparisons to provide big-picture insights and build evidence in a cohesive manner.

R1.4 Support development and implementation of reporting guidelines for impact studies

Our assessment of the evidence revealed a great degree of variation in study design, type of data, approach to using it and interpreting it. We observed variation in quality of the studies and strength of the findings and claims based on this. In addition to that, we encountered difficulties in synthesizing because of high variety in how study designs, methods, aims and findings were reported. We therefore recommend the development of reporting guidelines and standards for impact studies to improve completeness and consistency of reporting and therefore the strength of the integrated evidence base.

R1.5 Support Open Research infrastructures for data relevant to impact assessment

To enable better measurement and monitoring of Open Science impact, equitable access needs to be given to the data necessary to do so. Instead of relying on high-cost data sources, resources should be invested into independent and open infrastructures, similar to infrastructure to disseminate and access Open Science. Business models behind Open Science, i.e., who is profiting from practices and from providing data, should also be made more transparent so that potential biases in data can be investigated. Independent and open infrastructure can be created in ways to combat existing biases in data.

R1.6 Support evaluation approaches that address causality and long-term impact

Our analysis reveals that many Open Science impact evaluations rely on weak study designs that cannot establish causal attribution or capture longer-term effects. We recommend that

funding agencies and policy bodies prioritize and support evaluation approaches that address these methodological challenges. This includes supporting evaluation studies that: employ appropriate counterfactual designs to establish causal attribution; track impacts over medium to longer time horizons rather than focusing only on immediate uptake; integrate novel methodological approaches such as mixed-methods designs, AI-driven computational analysis, and cost-benefit frameworks; and account for contextual factors that moderate impact pathways.

Funding calls for impact evaluation should explicitly value methodological rigor over ease of implementation, and provide adequate resources for studies that can establish causal relationships rather than just document associations. This approach recognizes that robust impact evidence requires investment in appropriate methodology, but places the responsibility for methodological advancement on the research and evaluation community rather than expecting every implementing institution to become evaluation experts.

7.2. Improving the evidence base for measuring and evaluating impacts driven by Open Science

PathOS found that while some Open Science practices and some outcomes and impacts are heavily studied, others have had little attention paid to them or are completely understudied. Therefore, we make the following recommendations to improve the evidence base for measuring and evaluating impacts driven by Open Science.

R2.1 Study more Open Science interventions, outcomes and impacts and promote a diversity of evidence

Certain Open Science interventions, like Open Access publishing and Citizen Science, have been heavily and disproportionately studied because there is either existing data that enables this, and/or, there are established methods that make it possible for many to do so. This is an example of the “streetlight effect” which describes a phenomenon where certain areas are investigated disproportionately while others remain understudied due to the fact that the former are easier to study than the latter. In particular, the evidence base is lacking attention to how Open Science, outside of Citizen Science, drives societal impact; how transparency practices drive impact; and how Open Science drives economic impact. Data sources (and methods) to research understudied aspects of Open Science impact should be strategically developed by key stakeholders, overcoming biases and enabling research into open questions by thinking about new combinations of open (meta)data and infrastructures. Attention needs to be shifted

away from what already has been studied to not further incentivise additional research there. Interdisciplinary engagement, e.g., with social sciences and humanities, can also aid in diversifying what is investigated.

Additionally, we note a heavy reliance on quantitative data and an under-reliance on qualitative data and mixed methods to study Open Science impact. We recommend that current hierarchies of evidence are rethought and that a diversity of evidence should be promoted to establish evidence of Open Science impact. The types of evidence also need to be matched to respective goals and questions.

R2.2 Move focus in investigations from uptake to impact

To date, much of the evidence of impact relies on proxy measures of uptake to postulate impacts driven by Open Science interventions. To deepen the understanding of Open Science impact and improve monitoring, studies of actual impact are needed. Impact is a very wide, complex and diverse concept that allows room for different communities to focus on what is important for them to examine. Terminology has to be agreed on, with impacts defined in concrete and measurable ways. In addition, infrastructure has to be adapted to allow not only the measurement of uptake, but also of impact. Still, measuring uptake, e.g., through number of outputs made openly available, could be valuable for certain contexts, such as for smaller interventions that are unlikely to have a large measurable impact or to incentivise individual behaviour.

R2.3 Explicitly document negative results, not only successes

The literature that demonstrates evidence of Open Science impact suggests possible publication bias toward positive findings of impact. Since some of the literature, and some of the PathOS case studies, found null and sometimes negative effects, we recommend support for publishing studies that demonstrate this, which requires academic and funders' recognition. Evaluation of Open Science impact needs understanding not only of what works, but also what does not, and how various factors might influence whether an intervention does or does not work in a given context or who is excluded by a certain practice. Registering studies conducted in this context and sharing all outcomes would contribute to achieving a more balanced evidence base. We also recommend support for third-party evaluations of case studies or series to reduce publication bias. Studies are often conducted in environments where people are enthusiastic about Open Science practices, potentially driving positive effects.

R2.4 Stakeholders in the Open Science reform movement should take the initiative to define key evidence gaps from their standpoints

The Open Science movement is large, diverse, and dispersed globally. Therefore, a diversity of perspectives and sector expertise is needed to identify gaps in impact evidence, to ensure that future initiatives generate and gather data and study impact in ways that meet the needs and expectations of all. This also needs to include less-resourced stakeholders or those that are traditionally underrecognized, or so far structurally excluded, which might require specific funding. Key stakeholders in reform implementation, e.g., research-performing and research-funding organisations, can actively contribute by making their research information open (such as stated in the [Barcelona declaration](#)).

R2.5 Increase resources and support for impact studies

There is, in general, not enough policy support and funding for impact studies. To carry out the recommendations that follow, support should be increased at national, European and international levels. Resources currently used for closed data products and services, e.g., to pay fees, could be repurposed to make open tools available for everyone conducting impact studies. Additional support could be provided through teaching about impact, e.g., in doctoral programmes and research methods courses. Impact studies should be conducted by independent or at least multiple stakeholders; this should be considered when allocating resources.

R2.6 Establish PathOS 2.0: A systematic Open Science impact research initiative

PathOS identified significant evidence gaps in Open Science impact evaluation while demonstrating methodological approaches to address them through case studies. However, these case studies only partially filled the gaps, revealing the need for systematic, large-scale application of PathOS methods across diverse contexts and interventions.

We recommend establishing PathOS 2.0, a coordinated research initiative that would: systematically apply PathOS methodological frameworks (indicators, AI-driven analysis, mixed methods, CBA) across a broader range of Open Science practices and contexts to fill identified evidence gaps; maintain and continuously develop the PathOS OS Impact Indicator Handbook

through ongoing empirical validation and community input; extend CBA approaches to other Open Science interventions; coordinate data collection efforts that support rigorous impact evaluation across institutions and research domains; provide training and capacity building in methodological approaches; and systematically investigate additional impact pathways across academic, economic, and societal domains to understand how benefits interconnect.

PathOS 2.0 would build on proven foundations to create the comprehensive, systematic evidence base needed for evidence-based Open Science policy. This initiative would move to a systematic evaluation that can inform strategic decisions about Open Science investments and implementation approaches across diverse research contexts.

7.3. Increasing Open Science impact

Though the evidence is limited, it consistently shows that Open Access to research outputs, be they publications, data sets, or software, code or tools, drives a range of beneficial outcomes that lead to positive academic, societal and economic impacts. For instance, open outputs drive increased readership and reuse, with positive impacts on EDI and efficiency. Open Access publications are more likely to be used in policymaking, in healthcare settings, and industrial contexts, and reuse in each of these settings is known to drive beneficial impacts. Evidence also shows that Open Data and open-source software, code and tools have been successfully deployed in healthcare contexts in ways that drive beneficial health impacts at localised and global levels. In response to the body of evidence of Open Science impact synthesised and presented in this report, PathOS recommends the following to increase Open Science impact.

R3.1 Increase support for the diversification of participation in scientific research

More (effective) collaboration with a diversity of actors has long been considered a key aspect of Open Science (OECD 2015). Considerable attention has been paid to the diversification of research through Citizen Science and other participatory forms of research such as patient-led research. Considerable evidence shows that societal inclusion in research drives a range of outcomes, including strengthening social ties and group cohesion, democratising research, increases in scientific and topical knowledge and awareness, behaviour change, and reuse of research outputs by societal actors. In turn, these outcomes lead to empowerment of societal actors, benefits to equity, positive impacts on climate and environment, and to health and safety. In the academic context, this diversification has yielded efficiency benefits and been shown to enable data collection at scale and of good quality. However, collaboration amongst diverse academic actors remains one of the less explored aspects of Open Science.

A possible reason for this is that, to date, Open Science policy and funding has focused primarily on creating access to open outputs and has offered little more than gestures of support for societal inclusion (as illustrated by Chena et al. 2025). Despite this, the evidence shows that societal inclusion in the form of active participation drives positive academic and societal impact. Therefore, we call for increased policy support for this form of openness, and greater funding for the implementation of Citizen Science and other participatory research methods. For example, policies might require societal participation at all stages of publicly funded research, increasing inclusion already in the design phase.

Additionally, we see a need for Open Science initiatives to carefully consider how they can be redesigned to foster collaboration amongst researchers, especially to facilitate participation of marginalised or under-resourced researchers (e.g., based on geographic region, gender, race, ethnicity, disability, discipline, language or career stage). Regarding societal inclusion, they should attend to interactions with indigenous knowledge systems to ensure that they are equitable as defined by the CARE principles (Carroll et al. 2021).

R3.2 Increase support for equitable sharing of quality open outputs

PathOS generated evidence that open infrastructures that enable open and FAIR access to research outputs foster academic and economic impact, and societal access, and that the benefits of implementing them far outweigh the costs. Therefore, we recommend the promotion of shared and interoperable infrastructures, such as centralised repositories and integrated data platforms, to achieve economies of scale and reduce unnecessary duplication across institutions; sustainable and coordinated funding models for high-impact infrastructures and platforms; and collaboration and alignment of standards and protocols to enhance the global added value and reusability of Open Research output.

Additionally, to translate this support into action, more education and institutional support for best practices for sharing and reuse is needed within the academic community, as well as changes to the reward and recognition system, to create a more equitable incentive system. Attention must be paid to ensuring that all researchers have the support and resources for sharing, and that not just the resource-privileged are able to do so.

At the same time, to increase impact, quality and value are important considerations when sharing outputs. Therefore, mechanisms for quality assurance and curation of non-traditional outputs (e.g., data, code, methodological and analytic documentation, preprints) should be extended to increase their potential for impact. However, how quality is defined also depends on the users, intended impacts, and discipline and should be defined in context-appropriate ways. This requires discussions within communities of both producers and users of outputs.

PathOS evidence demonstrates that implementation quality matters more than the volume of open outputs. Repository choice affected outcomes more than repository existence, and UniProt's value stemmed from intensive curation rather than accessibility alone. This suggests that investments should prioritize fewer, higher-quality implementations over broad but superficial openness efforts.

R3.3 Attend to issues of equity and capacity in reuse

The impact of open outputs depends not only on their availability and quality (which can be supported on the side of the producer, as detailed above), but also upon the absorptive capacities of potential re-users, i.e., individual or organisational abilities to assimilate and apply external knowledge. This includes not only technical expertise but also access to resources and relevant infrastructure that goes beyond mere online accessibility. Hosseini et al. (2025) propose the term “meaningful access” (as opposed to physical access) to refer to knowledge made available in ways that optimise potential uptake amongst diverse users. For example, PathOS evidence shows that meaningful access to research outputs drives a range of beneficial academic, societal, and economic impacts, including empowerment and equity, impacts on climate and environment, and on health and safety. Interoperability, curation, and integration of data are key factors that transform open resources into actionable knowledge. These features increase the relevance, discoverability, and reusability of research outputs, enabling their translation into innovative products, services, and solutions.

Equally important is investing in user support, including training, documentation, and responsive technical assistance. These efforts can reduce access and learning costs, particularly for non-academic users such as SMEs, startups, and policymakers, thereby improving uptake and broadening the impact of Open Science initiatives.

We therefore recommend investing in training and support to ensure that meaningful access is created by those that share research outputs, including awareness campaigns about the availability of open outputs and training in reuse for non-academic actors. Specifically, it is important to ensure that industrial actors, and SMEs in particular, not only have access to open resources but also the capability to translate access into innovation, growth, and competitive advantage. Targeted support in this area will help democratise the benefits of Open Science and ensure that public investments in Open Research infrastructures deliver broad-based economic returns. Despite evidence of significant efficiency advantages such as reduced R&D costs, faster access to cutting-edge research, and improved product development timelines, access by SMEs to open outputs remains limited for lack of technical infrastructure, domain expertise, and personnel. These benefits are often concentrated in firms with high absorptive capacity or established relationships with research organisations, such as for large pharmaceutical companies active in the life science domain. To unlock the full potential of Open

Science for SMEs there is the need to expand and adapt Open Science services to better meet SME needs (e.g. by making data services more discoverable, user-friendly, and domain-specific) and invest in capacity-building for absorptive use.

R3.4 Expand efforts to increase transparency based on evidence

Evidence shows that transparency, by opening information on the who, what, why, when, and how of research processes supports reproducibility, and increased quality of knowledge, which may influence use and reuse. However, evidence of effective practices, including Open Methods practices such as pre-registration and open notebooks, is field-specific. As such, their applicability in expanded contexts should be carefully explored and tested. Transparency in peer review shows benefits through the publishing of peer review reports, but publishing reviewer identities remains problematic. Different risks might be associated with transparency for individuals from different backgrounds, disciplines, or career stages. These concerns should be further investigated and considered when expanding transparent practices.

R3.5 Balance the need for proprietary resources with the aims of openness

Evidence shows that there may be tensions between the potential of Open Science in driving innovation and concerns around intellectual property (IP), especially at the interface between academia and industry. While open sharing of data, publications, and software can accelerate discovery and reduce duplication, the protection of commercial interests is also critical and can create hesitation, particularly within industry. Developing guidance on IP frameworks in Open Science settings is key to fostering trust. Such guidance should clarify how and to what extent openness can coexist with appropriate protection of proprietary knowledge, or where it even goes well together, and outline contractual models for managing IP in shared research environments. Currently, outputs of most collaborative projects are closed by default except when required by funders. Through support and incentive measures, this could be reshaped to be more open from the start, while still granting exclusive rights on selected outputs, such as embargos or patents when necessary. At the same time, promoting pre-competitive collaboration models, where stakeholders jointly develop tools, data, or methods before entering competitive markets, can encourage greater openness without compromising commercial value, following the model of [patent pools](#) and non Open Access commons (requiring payment, registration, and/or with limited usage rights). Still, there is a need for the

Open Science community to discuss how they want public-private partnerships to work and what aspects of open sharing and of reserved access are needed.

8. References

- Apartis, S., G. Catalano, G. Consiglio, et al. 2024. *Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook*. <https://handbook.pathos-project.eu/>.
- Arshad, Zeeshaan, James Smith, Mackenna Roberts, et al. 2016. 'Open Access Could Transform Drug Discovery: A Case Study of JQ1'. *Expert Opinion on Drug Discovery* 11 (3): 321–32.
- Aschhoff, Birgit, Andreas H. Fier, and Heide Löhlein. 2006. 'Detecting Behavioural Additionality - an Empirical Study on the Impact of Public R&D Funding on Firms' Cooperative Behaviour in Germany'. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.908211>.
- Barbers, Irene, Franziska Stanzel, and Bernhard Mittermaier. 2022. 'Open Access Monitor Germany: Best Practice in Providing Metrics for Analysis and Decision-Making'. *Serials Review* 48 (1–2): 49–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2022.2066968>.
- Beagrie, N., and J. Houghton. 2013a. *The Value and Impact of the Archaeology Data Service: A Study and Methods for Enhancing Sustainability*. Charles Beagrie Ltd and Victoria University. https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/5509/1/ADSReport_final.pdf.
- Beagrie, N., and J. Houghton. 2013b. *The Value and Impact of the British Atmospheric Data Centre*. https://vuir.vu.edu.au/39092/1/2013_Beagrie%26Houghton_Value%26Impact_Brit_Atmospheric_Data_Centre.pdf.
- Beagrie, Neil, and John Houghton. 2012. *Economic Impact Evaluation of the Economic and Social Data Service*.
- Beagrie, Neil, and John Houghton. 2014. *The Value and Impact of Data Sharing and Curation. A Synthesis of Three Recent Studies of UK Research Data Centres*.
- Beagrie, Neil, and John Houghton. 2021. *Data-Driven Discovery: The Value and Impact of EMBL-EBI Managed Data Resources*.
- Bezuidenhout, Louise, Paola Castaño, Sabina Leonelli, Ismael Rafols, and Andrea Vargiu. 2024. *Introducing Case Studies in Monitoring Open Science*. November 16. <https://zenodo.org/records/14174180>.
- Bokonda, Patrick Loola, Khadija Ouazzani-Touhami, and Nissrine Souissi. 2019. 'Open Data Kit: Mobile Data Collection Framework For Developing Countries'. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering* 8 (12): 4749–54. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijitee.L3583.1081219>.

- Bornmann, Lutz, and Hans-Dieter Daniel. 2008. 'What Do Citation Counts Measure? A Review of Studies on Citing Behavior'. *Journal of Documentation* 64 (1): 45–80. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00220410810844150>.
- Bracco, Laetitia. 2022. 'Promoting Open Science through Bibliometrics: A Practical Guide to Build an Open Access Monitor'. *LIBER Quarterly: The Journal of the Association of European Research Libraries* 32 (1): 1. <https://doi.org/10.53377/lq.11545>.
- Bracco, Laetitia, Anne L'Hôte, Eric Jeangirard, and Didier Torny. 2022. 'Extending the Open Monitoring of Open Science'. April. <https://hal.science/hal-03651518>.
- Bryan, Kevin A., and Yasin Ozcan. 2021. 'The Impact of Open Access Mandates on Invention'. *The Review of Economics and Statistics* 103 (5): 954–67. https://doi.org/10.1162/rest_a_00926.
- Carroll, Stephanie Russo, Edit Herczog, Maui Hudson, Keith Russell, and Shelley Stall. 2021. 'Operationalizing the CARE and FAIR Principles for Indigenous Data Futures'. *Scientific Data* 8 (1): 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-00892-0>.
- Catalano, Gelsomina, Alessandra Caputo, Louis Colnot, et al. 2025a. *Deliverable 4.4 – Cost-Benefit Analysis of Open Science: Case Study Synthesis and UniProt and RCAAP Case Studies*. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/15731712>.
- Catalano, Gelsomina, Louis Colnot, Silvia Vignetti, Antonia Correia, Pedro Príncipe, Paulo Lopes, and Elisa Seminaroti. 2025b. *RCAAP Case Study*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15732145>.
- Catalano, Gelsomina, Erica Delugas, Silvia Vignetti, Alessandra Caputo, Izabella Martins Grapengiesser, Despoina Sousoni, Erika Balsyte, and Dimitris Pappas. 2025c. *UniProt Case Study and Factsheet*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15732022>.
- Chtena, Natascha, Juan Pablo Alperin, Esteban Morales, et al. 2025. 'Towards an Inclusive Open Science: Examining EDI and Public Participation in Policy Documents across Europe and the Americas'. *Royal Society Open Science* 12 (4). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.240857>.
- Coccia, Mario. 2021. 'Evolution and Structure of Research Fields Driven by Crises and Environmental Threats: The COVID-19 Research'. *Scientometrics* 126 (12): 9405–29. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-04172-x>.
- Cole, Nicki Lisa, Simon Apartis, Erika Balsyte, et al. 2023. *PathOS - D3.1 Case Studies for Evaluation of Open Science Impact*. October 31. <https://zenodo.org/records/10057051>.
- Cole, Nicki Lisa, Eva Kormann, Thomas Klebel, Simon Apartis, and Tony Ross-Hellauer. 2024. 'The Societal Impact of Open Science: A Scoping Review'. *Royal Society Open Science* 11 (6): 240286. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.240286>.

- Cole, Nicki Lisa, Sven Ulpts, Agata Bochynska, Eva Kormann, Matthew Good, Barbara Leitner, et al. 2024. 'Reproducibility and Replicability of Qualitative Research: An Integrative Review of Concepts, Barriers and Enablers'. Preprint, OSF, December 23. <https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/n5zkw>.
- Cole, Nicki Lisa, Sven Ulpts, Agata Bochynska, Eva Kormann, Matthew Good, and Tony Ross-Hellauer. 2024. *Reproducibility and Replicability of Qualitative Research: An Integrative Review of Concepts, Barriers and Enablers*.
- Conti, Annamaria, Christian Peukert, and Maria Roche. 2021. 'Beefing IT up for Your Investor? Open Sourcing and Startup Funding: Evidence from GitHub'. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3883936>.
- Dekker, Ron, Istvan Karasz, and Lennart Stoy. 2023. *PathOS - D1.1 Open Science Intervention Logic*. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/10418573>.
- Delugas, Erica, Gelsomina Catalano, and Silvia Vignetti. 2025. *PathOS - D4.2 Methodological Note on the CBA of Open Science Practices (update)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17091711>.
- European Commission. 2019. 'About the Open Science Monitor'. June 28. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/open-science-monitor/about-open-science-monitor_en.
- European Commission, K. Blind, M. Böhm, et al. 2021. *The Impact of Open Source Software and Hardware on Technological Independence, Competitiveness and Innovation in the EU Economy*. Brussels.
- Fell, Michael J. 2019. 'The Economic Impacts of Open Science: A Rapid Evidence Assessment'. *Publications* 7 (3): 46. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications7030046>.
- Field, Sarahanne. 2022. *Charting the Constellation of Science Reform*. University of Groningen. <https://doi.org/10.33612/diss.229114775>.
- Giffoni, Francesco, and Silvia Vignetti. 2019. 'Assessing the Socioeconomic Impact of Research Infrastructures: A Systematic Review of Existing Approaches and the Role of Cost-Benefit Analysis'. *L'industria*, no. 1: 75–102. <https://ideas.repec.org//a/mul/j0hje1/doi10.1430-94060y2019i1p75-102.html>.
- Giovani, Baldissera. 2017. 'Open Data for Research and Strategic Monitoring in the Pharmaceutical and Biotech Industry'. *Data Science Journal* 16 (April): 18. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2017-018>.
- Haddad, Carolina R., and Anna Bergek. 2023. 'Towards an Integrated Framework for Evaluating Transformative Innovation Policy'. *Research Policy* 52 (2): 104676. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2022.104676>.

- Hosseini, Mohammad, Serge P. J. M. Horbach, Kristi Holmes, and Tony Ross-Hellauer. 2025. 'Open Science at the Generative AI Turn: An Exploratory Analysis of Challenges and Opportunities'. *Quantitative Science Studies* 6 (January): 22–45. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00337.
- Houghton, John, and Peter Sheehan. 2006. 'The Economic Impact of Enhanced Access to Research Findings.' *CSES Working Paper (No. 23)*.
- Houghton, John, and Peter Sheehan. 2009. 'Estimating the Potential Impacts of Open Access to Research Findings'. *Economic Analysis and Policy* 39 (1): 127–42. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0313-5926\(09\)50048-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0313-5926(09)50048-3).
- Houghton, John, Alma Swan, and Sheridan Brown. 2011. *Access to Research and Technical Information in Denmark*. Monograph. With John Houghton, Alma Swan, and Sheridan Brown. <https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/272603/>.
- Huang, Chun-Kai, Cameron Neylon, Lucy Montgomery, et al. 2024. 'Open Access Research Outputs Receive More Diverse Citations'. *Scientometrics* 129 (2): 825–45. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-023-04894-0>.
- Jahn, Najko, Thomas Klebel, David Pride, Petr Knoth, and Tony Ross-Hellauer. 2022. 'Quantifying the Influence of Open Access on Innovation and Patents'. *Open Research Europe* 2 (May): 64. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14680.1>.
- Karasz, Istvan, Lennart Stoy, Elisa Seminaroti, and Izabella Martins Grapengiesser. 2024. *PathOS - D1.3 Key Impact Pathways for the Open Science Framework*. April 30. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.11108567>.
- Klebel, Thomas, and Vincent Traag. 2025. 'Introduction to Structural Causal Models in Science Studies'. Preprint, OSF, March 12. https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/4bw9e_v3.
- Klebel, Thomas, Vincent Traag, Ioanna Grypari, Lennart Stoy, and Tony Ross-Hellauer. 2025. 'The Academic Impact of Open Science: A Scoping Review'. *Royal Society Open Science* 12 (3): 241248. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.241248>.
- Kobayashi, Shinji, Luis Falcón, Hamish Fraser, et al. 2021. 'Using Open Source, Open Data, and Civic Technology to Address the COVID-19 Pandemic and Infodemic'. *Yearbook of Medical Informatics* 30 (01): 038–043. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0041-1726488>.
- Leonelli, Sabina. 2018. 'Rethinking Reproducibility as a Criterion for Research Quality'. In *Research in the History of Economic Thought and Methodology*, edited by Luca Fiorito, Scott Scheall, and Carlos Eduardo Suprinyak, vol. 36. Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S0743-41542018000036B009>.

- Longino, Helen E. 1990. *Science as Social Knowledge*. Princeton University Press. <https://press.princeton.edu/books/paperback/9780691020518/science-as-social-knowledge>.
- Longino, Helen E. 2001. *The Fate of Knowledge*. Princeton University Press.
- Look, H., and Marsh, K. 2012. *Benefits of Open Access to Scholarly Research Outputs to the Public Sector. A Report for the Open Access Implementation Group*.
- Marshall, Zack, Fern Brunger, Vivian Welch, Shabnam Asghari, and Chris Kaposy. 2018. 'Open Availability of Patient Medical Photographs in Google Images Search Results: Cross-Sectional Study of Transgender Research'. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 20 (2): e70. <https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.8787>.
- Munafo, M. R., B. A. Nosek, D. V. M. Bishop, et al. 2017. 'A Manifesto for Reproducible Science'. *Nat Hum Behav* 1 (January): 0021. PubMed-not-MEDLINE (33954258). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-016-0021>.
- OECD. 2015. *Making Open Science a Reality*. OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers No. 25. Vol. 25. OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5jrs2f963zs1-en>.
- Ozaygen, Alkim, Lucy Montgomery, Cameron Neylon, et al. 2020. 'More Readers in More Places: The Benefits of Open Access for Scholarly Books'. Preprint, Zenodo, September 10. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014905>.
- Pawson, Ray, Trisha Greenhalgh, Gill Harvey, and Kieran Walshe. 2005. 'Realist Review - a New Method of Systematic Review Designed for Complex Policy Interventions'. *Journal of Health Services Research & Policy* 10 (1_suppl): 21-34. <https://doi.org/10.1258/1355819054308530>.
- Rafols, Ismael, Ingeborg Meijer, and Jordi Molas-Gallart. 2024. 'Monitoring Open Science as Transformative Change: Towards a Systemic Framework'. *F1000Research* 13 (April): 320. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.148290.1>.
- Ravenscroft, James, Maria Liakata, Amanda Clare, and Daniel Duma. 2017. 'Measuring Scientific Impact beyond Academia: An Assessment of Existing Impact Metrics and Proposed Improvements'. *PLOS ONE* 12 (3): e0173152. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0173152>.
- Ross-Hellauer, Tony, Thomas Klebel, and Alkis Pitelis. 2022. *Protocol for Scoping Reviews of (1) Academic, (2) Societal and (3) Economic Impacts of Open Science*. October 31. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/GM57C>.
- Ross-Hellauer, Tony, Stefan Reichmann, Nicki Lisa Cole, Angela Fessl, Thomas Klebel, and Nancy Pontika. 2022. 'Dynamics of Cumulative Advantage and Threats to Equity in Open

Science: A Scoping Review'. *Royal Society Open Science* 9 (1): 211032. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.211032>.

Stavropoulos, Petros, Ioanna Grypari, Haris Papageorgiou, Vincent Traag, Zeynep Anli, Tim Willemse, Despoina Sousoni, et al. 2025. *PathOS - D3.3 Open Science Impact Indicators for Case Studies Final Report*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17543431>.

Stavropoulos, Petros, Ioanna Grypari, Haris Papageorgiou, Vincent Traag, Zeynep Anli, Tim Willemse, Despoina Sousoni, et al. 2025. *PathOS - D3.4 Data and Tools for the Long-term Evaluation of Open Science*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17578155>.

Stoy, Lennart, Izabella Martins Grapengiesser, Elisa Seminaroti, Nicki Lisa Cole, Lena Tshipouri, and Tereza Simova. 2025. *PathOS - D1.3 Key Impact Pathways for the Open Science Framework (update)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16994082>.

Sullivan, Kevin P., Brennan-Tonetta, and Lucas J. Marxen. 2017. *Economic Impacts of the Research Collaboratory for Structural Bioinformatics (RCSB) Protein Data Bank*.

Sweeny, Dr Kim, Dr Masha Fridman, and Professor Bruce Rasmussen. 2017. *Estimating the Value and Impact of Nectar Virtual Laboratories*.

Tripp, Simon, and Martin Grueber. 2011. *The Economic Impacts of Human Genome Project*.

Tshipouri, Lena, Sofia Liarti, Silvia Vignetti, and Izabella Martins-Grapengiesser. 2025. 'The Economic Impact of Open Science: A Scoping Review'. Preprint, OSF, February 26. https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/kqse5_v1.

UNESCO. 2021a. *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546>.

UNESCO. 2021b. *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. UNESCO. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949.locale=en>.

Wadman, Meredith. 2013. 'Economic Return from Human Genome Project Grows'. *Nature*, ahead of print, June 12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature.2013.13187>.

Wilkinson, Helen, Dione Hills, Alexandra Penn, and Pete Barbrook-Johnson. 2021. 'Building a System-Based Theory of Change Using Participatory Systems Mapping'. *Evaluation* 27 (1): 80–101. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356389020980493>.

Williams, Heidi L. 2013. 'Intellectual Property Rights and Innovation: Evidence from the Human Genome'. *Journal of Political Economy* 121 (1): 1–27.

9. Annexes

Annex A. Mechanisms of Open Science Impact

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We define Open Science as a diverse coalition of researchers, policymakers, managers and administrators based in academic institutions, funding organisations, disciplinary bodies (scholarly societies) and industry (including publishers). As Field (2022, 190) has noted, Open Science is perhaps best seen as “a constellation of multiple, diverse communities of practice, with shifting, mutable boundaries, in which a collective identity and enterprise is being continually negotiated.” As such, it encompasses various practices, underpinned by multiple values and principles. The 2021 UNESCO definition (UNESCO 2021) categorises Open Science as involving practices of open scientific knowledge, Open Science infrastructures, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems. These practices are underpinned by values such as quality and integrity, collective benefit, and equity and fairness, as well as a range of principles including transparency, responsibility and collaboration.

This diversity of aims, activities and intended outcomes, along with methodological issues regarding the heavily correlational nature of many studies, makes drawing consistent chains of causality across this picture difficult. Within the tradition of realist evaluation (a theory-led method for social programme evaluation), the principle of generative causality “holds that, to infer a causal outcome (O) between two events (X and Y), one needs to understand the underlying mechanism (M) that connects them and the context (C) in which the relationship occurs” (Pawson et al. 2005, 21–22).

Within Open Science, what are those key mechanisms? We conceptualise them based on philosopher Helen Longino’s argument that there are three senses in which we can understand “knowledge” (Longino 2001, 80ff.):

- **Content:** Knowledge as “outputs”, i.e., the outcomes of knowledge-productive practices. Content can be represented and stored mentally, bodily or materially (via documents and other media) and can be shared.
- **Process:** Knowledge as “knowledge productive practices”, i.e., the practices whereby inputs like research questions and hypotheses become outputs in the form of scientific content.

- **Agency:** Knowledge as “knowing”, i.e., the interrelation of subject (the knower), representation (content, as described above), and the object or objects of knowledge. Longino understands the knowing subject to be essentially (and formatively) limited by their location in time, space and (scientific) society, who are hence never mere followers of “context-independent and value-neutral methodological rules.” Hence, “the attribution of knowledge in the relational sense must include some acknowledgment of the social (i.e., interdependent) character of the subjects to which knowledge is attributed.”

In what follows, we propose a model of three underlying Open Science mechanisms which map to Longino’s three senses of knowledge:

- **Access:** Extension of knowledge as content, i.e., increasing the availability and manipulability of research objects, primarily to enable reuse and boost research impact for collective benefit.
- **Transparency:** Enabling openness of knowledge as process, i.e., increasing knowledge about underlying research practices and decision-making, primarily to boost the accountability, integrity and quality of research.
- **Participation:** Extension of knowledge as agency, i.e., enable new forms of researcher collaboration and inclusion of a diversity of other types of actors (like the public in Citizen Science), primarily to increase equity, diversity and inclusion and thus boost the societal relevance of research.

In the next section, we retrace the development of Open Science through engagement with foundational texts including key vision documents from supra-national bodies like OECD, National Academy of Sciences, UNESCO, and the European Commission, as well as key grassroots manifestos or declarations of principles regarding specific elements of Open Science. In so doing, we aim to analytically present the key rationales presented for these mechanisms.

Increased access to research outputs

Open Science is most commonly understood as concerned to increase access to research outputs (cf. Chtena et al. 2025; Leonelli 2023). For example, it has been defined by the OECD as “efforts to make the output of publicly funded research more widely accessible in digital format” (OECD 2015, 9), by the European Commission (EC) as “sharing knowledge as early as possible” (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission) 2016, 34), and by the US National Academy of Sciences (NAS) as “free availability and usability” of publications, data, code (Committee on Toward an Open Science Enterprise et al. 2018, 1).

If we take the early stages of the Open Science movement to have been shaped primarily by the Open Access movement in the early 2000s, we can see *Access* as the key mechanism

motivating early Open Science. Hence foundational documents like the Budapest Open Access Initiative declaration called for increased sharing of research publications to replace the toll-access framed as the closed scholarship model of the traditional publishing industry, whether through Open Access publishing or author self-archiving of manuscripts (Chan et al. 2002). Later, following reports like the OECD's "OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding" (OECD 2007), and with deepening reflection on the range of legitimate grounds for not sharing data (including data sensitivity, data protection, and security), the movement for FAIR data emerged. Under a mantra of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary", a largely infrastructural community proposed that where openness was not possible, data should at least be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable for the purposes of "extracting maximum benefit" (Wilkinson et al. 2016, 1). The FAIR principles were subsequently extended to research software (Barker et al. 2022). Open Science also advocates sharing of a range of other elements of research workflows: preprints (Bourne et al. 2017), protocols (Giraldo et al. 2018), workflows (Gustafsson et al. 2025), hardware (Arancio 2021) and even peer review reports (Ross-Hellauer 2017).

As indicated by the quote from the FAIR principles, rationales for increased access have most commonly centred on unlocking unrealised value, especially in terms of "Increasing the return on public investments" (OECD 2007, 9) by "accelerating research" (OECD 2015, 7) and thus boosting "innovation" in science, industry and society (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission) 2016, 47). In Figure A.1 we present a simplified schema of the *Access* mechanism and its intended benefits. Here, *Access* primarily enables *Reuse* which boosts "*Impact*" through accelerated and increased academic, societal and economic research and innovation. Positive effects on *Equity, diversity and inclusion* in science and society were envisioned, but as downstream effects of more egalitarian access to outputs. For instance, in the Budapest Open Access Initiative, access was foreseen to "share the learning of the rich with the poor ... and lay the foundation for uniting humanity in a common intellectual conversation" (Chan et al. 2002).

Figure A.1. Schema of the Access mechanism, its interactions, and intended effects

Increased transparency of research processes

As an additional objective, Open Science also aims to *increase transparency in research processes*. *Access* and *Transparency* can be easily conflated but they have different functions and aim for interrelated though distinct ends. With *Access*, the emphasis is on the sharing and manipulability of research outputs (i.e., publications, data, methods and tools) to enable others to make use of them (as inputs) in their future activities. But *Transparency* is about perception, not action; visibility not manipulability. *Transparency* aims rather to foster understanding regarding the origin of research objects — the processes through which they were created — to foster greater credibility. Whereas the *Access* movement emerged originally from concerns to remove paywalls from papers and increase data-sharing, the emergence of *Transparency* as a key theme in Open Science came via the integration of existing movements for Research Integrity and increased reproducibility.

Research Integrity, a branch of research ethics concerned with adherence to norms and guidance on best practice, has a long history. Many of its key problems, such as incomplete reporting and manipulation or fabrication of data, were already diagnosed by Charles Babbage in his *Reflections on the Decline of Science in England, And Some of Its Causes* in 1830 (Babbage 2013). Through the 2000s, disciplinary communities (especially in the biomedical and psychological sciences) began to reckon anew with a perceived lack of robustness in reported literature. By the early- to mid-2010s, warnings of a “reproducibility crisis” were common (Baker 2016; Munafò et al. 2017), fuelled by impactful multi-lab studies seeming to show that many influential results in these statistics-heavy disciplines failed replication (Ebersole et al. 2020; Errington et al. 2014). In their *Manifesto for Reproducible Science*, Munafò et al. diagnosed the key stakes:

Claims become credible by the community reviewing, critiquing, extending and reproducing the supporting evidence. However, without transparency, claims only achieve credibility based on trust in the confidence or authority of the originator. Transparency is superior to trust. Open science refers to the process of making the content and process of producing evidence and claims transparent and accessible to others. (Munafò et al. 2017, 5)

These are very different concerns than those of “unlocking value” or “uniting rich and poor”. Rather, it is the quality of research that is at stake, and the perceived corrective is increases in transparency to restrict researcher’s degrees of freedom to engage in questionable research practices and enable auditing, thus fostering integrity, trust and accountability. Functionally, of

course, there is large overlap. Sharing data, analysis scripts, protocols, etc. support both *Access* and *Transparency*. Yet the difference can be readily seen not only in aims and ends, but also in activities. Not all *Transparency* activities imply the sharing of outputs. For instance, a key aspect of “Open Peer Review” is revealing reviewer identities to authors, under the logic that this may increase reviewer accountability and rigour (evidence on this effect is decidedly underwhelming, but that is another story). While in some systems, reviewers can sign their names to public reports, in others, disclosure occurs to the author only, but not the public (Ross-Hellauer 2017). To take another example, pre-registration has the aim of researchers fixing their research questions and methods in advance of data collection to avoid possibilities of data-dredging and post-hoc hypothesising (Simmons et al. 2022). Registered reports encourage researchers to submit these elements for peer review before data collection, ensuring in advance robustness of research plans and guaranteeing publication (upon resubmission) of results regardless of outcome to mitigate publication bias (Chambers and Tzavella 2022). But pre-registrations can be kept closed until study publication and still fulfil the registration requirement, and no part of registered report studies are publicly shared until publication.

With these two examples, the point is that *Transparency*, though it is often achieved via sharing of outputs, is not *Access*. It is information-sharing to open the black-box of scientific workflows on the who, where, what, why, when and how of knowledge-producing practices, to enable interrogability, accountability, and trust in research and amongst researchers. Its overall aims are, in the words of Munafo (2017) et al. to “maximize research quality” and thus “maximize the efficiency of the research community's use of the public's financial investment in research”.

Considerations of *Transparency* were already present in the EC and NAS reports previously cited, though the focus was still predominantly on the sharing of outputs rather than transparency *per se*. The EC acknowledged research integrity as a “key driver of Open Science”, emphasising the potential of Open Data to build trust amongst researchers and the general public (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission) 2016, 52). NAS stated “the openness of data is seen as being critical to ... enhancing reproducibility” and that “data, code, and workflows should be available and cited” (Committee on Toward an Open Science Enterprise et al. 2018, 28). Hence, we might say that where the Research Integrity/reproducibility faction of the Open Science movement prescribed greater attendance to the importance of transparency of processes, this still was largely interpreted amongst decision-makers as enabling sharing of outputs, and still largely framed it as the project of maximum return-on-investment.

Figure A.2 now adds these new elements regarding the *Transparency* mechanism and its intended effects to show their interactions with the elements identified for *Access*. In short, *Transparency* aims primarily to increase research *Quality* by making visible research processes (thus decreasing researcher degrees of freedom and increasing accountability). Doing so is

envisioned to have direct effects on overall *Efficiency* of research. There are interactions between *Quality* and *Reuse* (on the logic that research objects of higher *Quality* will be more reusable and useful, and that *Reuse* involves assessments and feedback regarding quality). *Transparency* also interacts with *Access*, as sharing of outputs is a major means to visibility, and transparency regarding the contexts of creation is a major factor in supporting the reusability of outputs.

Figure A.2. Schema of the Access and Transparency mechanisms, their interactions, and intended effects

Increased participation of diverse actors

A third mechanism is *Participation*. Referring to his indebtedness to the work of others, Newton famously said, "if I have seen further, it is by standing on the shoulders of giants" (quoted in Chen 2003). Knowledge generation is essentially collaborative. Researchers do not only build on other's work though. They help shape it through diverse forms of collaboration and critique. The age of "big science", with its increasing specialisation and reliance on expensive infrastructure, has led to big collaboration in many disciplines (Ribeiro et al. 2018). At the same time, changing theories regarding the science-society relationship, signified by labels like "Mode1" and "Mode2" (Gibbons et al. 1994), "Triple Helix" (Leydesdorff and Etzkowitz 1998), "Quadruple Helix" (Carayannis and Campbell 2009), "Post-Normal Science" (Funtowicz and Ravetz 1993) and "Responsible Research and Innovation" (Owen et al. 2012), have led to new conceptions of non-academics as research actors.

Drawing inspiration from the social-networking power of “Web 2.0”, contributory platforms like Facebook and Wikipedia, researchers and policymakers saw great potential for digitally empowered participation in research. Michael Nielsen claimed that “[n]ew networking tools hold out the possibility of marshalling large collaborations of researchers who will be able to tackle problems more quickly and effectively than what is feasible today” (Nielsen 2014). The OECD (2015, 7) listed “open collaboration enabled through ICTs” as one of three core aspects of Open Science (the others being Open Access and Open Data). In the words of the EC, “Open Science is to science what Web 2.0 was to social and economic transactions: allowing end users to be producers of ideas, relations and services and in doing so enabling new working models, new social relationships and leading to a new *modus operandi* for science” (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission) 2016, 33). Their report foresaw a future that was “global, networked and open” and where “[m]any more actors will take part in different ways” (ibid. 55). Citizen Science, a previously separate movement with its own history dating back to the late 1980s (Haklay et al. 2021), was hence welcomed under the banner of Open Science, seen as central to enabling Open Science participation of non-academics. A section of the 2015 EC report titled “Making science more inclusive” cited the value of Citizen Science as a new “data-source” that “reinforces public engagement and can re-direct research agendas towards issues of concern to citizens” (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission) 2016, 53) (EC OTW 2015, p.53). Similarly, the NAS report signalled the potential for “[b]roader participation in research” and the value of “expanding opportunities for citizen scientists to contribute to scientific advances” (Committee on Toward an Open Science Enterprise et al. 2018, 1).

Yet the terms of this participation, especially of non-traditional research actors, sometimes took an instrumentalist tone, seen in statements like that of the EC: “just as people offer spare rooms via AirBnB, why shouldn’t they be allowed to offer spare brain power via citizen science?” (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission) 2016, 34). And the potentials for collaborative participation to increase not only efficiency, but also equity, diversity and inclusion, were seen by some to be underexplored. Especially in light of a predominant conception of Open Science primarily in terms of *Access*, as the sharing of outputs, Open Science was argued to be instrumentalist (Shelley-Egan et al. 2020) or to primarily empower “neoliberal market-like organization” through “platform capitalism” (Mirowski 2018). Awareness was also growing that Open Science interventions could have unintended negative consequences upon equity and inclusion for the populations Open Science was originally supposed to help (Ross-Hellauer et al. 2022).

A pioneer in leading this conversation was the OCSDnet project, led by Leslie Chan, whose manifesto asked “what values have been absent from existing discussions. To whom does knowledge belong? Whose voice counts in science? And how can we increase

people's participation and agency in scientific production?" (OCSDnet 2017). In response to such concerns, UNESCO led an attempt to build global consensus in defining the aims and values of Open Science, leading to *The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science* (UNESCO 2021). The report amounts to a normative reevaluation of Open Science when compared to the earlier EC, OECD and NAS reports. Three of its four guiding values (collective benefit, equity and fairness, diversity and inclusiveness) centre participatory aspects. Efficiency is relegated to the background, mentioned only under the last principle, "sustainability", and defined as in the service of participation: "to be as efficient and impactful as possible by building on long-term practices, services, infrastructures and funding models to ensure participation of scientists from less-privileged countries or institutions." On this basis, the meaning of *Participation* has broadened. Open Science, in the UNESCO recommendation:

[P]rovides the basis for citizen and community involvement in the generation of knowledge and for an enhanced dialogue between scientists, policymakers and practitioners, entrepreneurs and community members, giving all stakeholders a voice in developing research that is compatible with their concerns, needs and aspirations." (UNESCO 2021, 13–14)

As such, the scope of Open Science now includes elements associated with the agenda of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). Participatory "co-production of knowledge" should enable inclusion of non-academic publics across the "research cycle" via "new forms of collaboration and work such as crowdfunding, crowdsourcing and scientific volunteering", including in processes of agenda-setting and application, as well as inquiry. In addition, epistemic justice is thematised via a commitment to "Open dialogue with other knowledge systems", i.e. "dialogue between different knowledge holders, that recognizes the richness of diverse knowledge systems and epistemologies and diversity of knowledge producers in line with the 2001 UNESCO Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity." In so doing, Open Science should "promote the inclusion of knowledge from traditionally marginalized scholars" and avoid extractivism through "respect for knowledge sovereignty and governance, and the recognition of rights of knowledge holders to receive a fair and equitable share of benefits that may arise from the utilization of their knowledge" (cf. the CARE principles, Carroll et al. 2021).

Figure A.3 now includes the *Participation* mechanism to complete our schema of the Open Science mechanisms, their interactions and intended effects. We can see that *Participation* functions primarily to foster *Equity, Diversity and Inclusion* – now no longer just the downstream effect of increased possibilities of more egalitarian conditions of *Reuse*, but as a direct aim in itself. Such conditions are aimed ultimately to increase the *Relevance* of research (its responsiveness to societally relevant issues), as well as *Solidarity* in terms of global cohesion and respect.

Figure A.3. Schema of the Access, Transparency and Participation mechanisms, their interactions, and intended effects

References

- Arancio, Julietta Cecilia. 2021. 'Opening Up The Tools For Doing Science: The Case Of The Global Open Science Hardware Movement'. *International Journal of Engineering, Social Justice, and Peace* 8 (2): 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.24908/ijesjp.v8i2.13997>.
- Babbage, Charles. 2013. *Reflections on the Decline of Science in England, and on Some of Its Causes*. Cambridge Library Collection - Mathematics. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139381048>.
- Baker, Monya. 2016. '1,500 Scientists Lift the Lid on Reproducibility'. *Nature* 533 (7604): 7604. <https://doi.org/10.1038/533452a>.
- Barker, Michelle, Neil P. Chue Hong, Daniel S. Katz, et al. 2022. 'Introducing the FAIR Principles for Research Software'. *Scientific Data* 9 (1): 622. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>.

- Bourne, Philip E., Jessica K. Polka, Ronald D. Vale, and Robert Kiley. 2017. 'Ten Simple Rules to Consider Regarding Preprint Submission'. *PLoS Computational Biology* 13 (5): e1005473. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1005473>.
- Carayannis, Elias G., and David F.J. Campbell. 2009. "Mode 3" and "Quadruple Helix": Toward a 21st Century Fractal Innovation Ecosystem'. *International Journal of Technology Management* 46 (3–4): 201–34. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJTM.2009.023374>.
- Carroll, Stephanie Russo, Edit Herczog, Maui Hudson, Keith Russell, and Shelley Stall. 2021. 'Operationalizing the CARE and FAIR Principles for Indigenous Data Futures'. *Scientific Data* 8 (1): 108. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-00892-0>.
- Chambers, Christopher D., and Loukia Tzavella. 2022. 'The Past, Present and Future of Registered Reports'. *Nature Human Behaviour* 6 (1): 29–42. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-021-01193-7>.
- Chan, Leslie, Darius Cuplinskas, Michael Eisen, et al. 2002. 'Budapest Open Access Initiative'. <https://web.archive.org/web/20171213093708/http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>.
- Chen, Chaomei. 2003. 'On the Shoulders of Giants'. In *Mapping Scientific Frontiers: The Quest for Knowledge Visualization*, edited by Chaomei Chen. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4471-0051-5_5.
- Chtena, Natascha, Juan Pablo Alperin, Esteban Morales, et al. 2025. 'Towards an Inclusive Open Science: Examining EDI and Public Participation in Policy Documents across Europe and the Americas'. *Royal Society Open Science* 12 (4). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.240857>.
- Committee on Toward an Open Science Enterprise, Board on Research Data and Information, Policy and Global Affairs, and National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. 2018. *Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research*. National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/25116>.
- Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission). 2016. *Open Innovation, Open Science, Open to the World: A Vision for Europe*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/061652>.
- Ebersole, Charles R., Maya B. Mathur, Erica Baranski, et al. 2020. 'Many Labs 5: Testing Pre-Data-Collection Peer Review as an Intervention to Increase Replicability'. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science* 3 (3): 309–31. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2515245920958687>.
- Errington, Timothy M, Elizabeth Iorns, William Gunn, Fraser Elisabeth Tan, Joelle Lomax, and Brian A Nosek. 2014. 'An Open Investigation of the Reproducibility of Cancer Biology Research'. *eLife* 3 (December): e04333. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.04333>.

- Field, Sarahanne. 2022. *Charting the Constellation of Science Reform*. University of Groningen. <https://doi.org/10.33612/diss.229114775>.
- Funtowicz, Silvio O., and Jerome R. Ravetz. 1993. 'Science for the Post-Normal Age'. *Futures* 25 (7): 739–55. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-3287\(93\)90022-L](https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-3287(93)90022-L).
- Gibbons, Michael, Camille Limoges, Helga Nowotny, Simon Schwartzman, Peter Scott, and Martin Trow. 1994. *The New Production of Knowledge: The Dynamics of Science and Research in Contemporary Societies*. SAGE.
- Giraldo, Olga, Alexander Garcia, and Oscar Corcho. 2018. 'A Guideline for Reporting Experimental Protocols in Life Sciences'. *PeerJ* 6 (May): e4795. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.4795>.
- Gustafsson, Ove Johan Ragnar, Sean R. Wilkinson, Finn Bacall, et al. 2025. 'WorkflowHub: A Registry for Computational Workflows'. *Scientific Data* 12 (1): 837. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04786-3>.
- Haklay, Mordechai (Muki), Daniel Dörler, Florian Heigl, Marina Manzoni, Susanne Hecker, and Katrin Vohland. 2021. 'What Is Citizen Science? The Challenges of Definition'. In *The Science of Citizen Science*, edited by Katrin Vohland, Anne Land-Zandstra, Luigi Ceccaroni, et al. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_2.
- Leonelli, Sabina. 2023. *Philosophy of Open Science*. Elements in the Philosophy of Science. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009416368>.
- Leydesdorff, Loet, and Henry Etzkowitz. 1998. 'The Triple Helix as a Model for Innovation Studies'. *Science and Public Policy* 25 (3): 195–203. <https://doi.org/10.1093/spp/25.3.195>.
- Longino, Helen E. 2001. *The Fate of Knowledge*. Princeton University Press.
- Mirowski, Philip. 2018. 'The Future(s) of Open Science'. *Social Studies of Science* 48 (2): 171–203. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306312718772086>.
- Munafò, Marcus R., Brian A. Nosek, Dorothy V. M. Bishop, et al. 2017. 'A Manifesto for Reproducible Science'. *Nature Human Behaviour* 1 (1): 0021. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-016-0021>.
- Nielsen, Michael. 2014. *Reinventing Discovery: The New Era of Networked Science*. Princeton University Press.
- OCSDnet. 2017. 'Open Science Manifesto'. OCSDnet. <https://ocsdnet.org/manifesto/open-science-manifesto/>.
- OECD. 2007. *OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding*. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264034020-en-fr>.

- OECD. 2015. *Making Open Science a Reality*. OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers No. 25. Vol. 25. OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5jrs2f963zs1-en>.
- Owen, Richard, Phil Macnaghten, and Jack Stilgoe. 2012. 'Responsible Research and Innovation: From Science in Society to Science for Society, with Society'. *Science and Public Policy* 39 (6): 751–60. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scs093>.
- Pawson, Ray, Trisha Greenhalgh, Gill Harvey, and Kieran Walshe. 2005. 'Realist Review - a New Method of Systematic Review Designed for Complex Policy Interventions'. *Journal of Health Services Research & Policy* 10 (1_suppl): 21–34. <https://doi.org/10.1258/1355819054308530>.
- Ribeiro, Leonardo Costa, Márcia Siqueira Rapini, Leandro Alves Silva, and Eduardo Motta Albuquerque. 2018. 'Growth Patterns of the Network of International Collaboration in Science'. *Scientometrics* 114 (1): 159–79. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-017-2573-x>.
- Ross-Hellauer, Tony. 2017. 'What Is Open Peer Review? A Systematic Review'. *F1000Research* 6 (August): 588. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.11369.2>.
- Ross-Hellauer, Tony, Stefan Reichmann, Nicki Lisa Cole, Angela Fessl, Thomas Klebel, and Nancy Pontika. 2022. 'Dynamics of Cumulative Advantage and Threats to Equity in Open Science: A Scoping Review'. *Royal Society Open Science* 9 (1): 211032. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.211032>.
- Shelley-Egan, Clare, Mads Dahl Gjefsen, and Rune Nydal. 2020. 'Consolidating RRI and Open Science: Understanding the Potential for Transformative Change'. *Life Sciences, Society and Policy* 16 (1): 7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40504-020-00103-5>.
- Simmons, Brooke D., Chris Lintott, Steven Reece, et al. 2022. 'Disaster, Infrastructure and Participatory Knowledge: The Planetary Response Network'. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice* 7 (1): 21. <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.392>.
- UNESCO. 2021. *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546>.
- Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, et al. 2016. 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship'. *Scientific Data* 3 (1): 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

Annex B. Unlocking the Insights from the PathOS Case Studies

The factsheet can be downloaded in HD quality from https://pathos-project.eu/images/Case_Studies/Unlocking%20the%20Insights%20from%20PathOS%20Case%20Studies%202.pdf. For easy reference we copy it below.

UNLOCKING THE INSIGHTS FROM THE PATHOS CASE STUDIES

PathOS is a Horizon Europe project aiming to collect concrete evidence of Open Science effects, study the pathways of Open Science practices, from input to output, outcome and impact, including the consideration of enabling factors and key barriers.

The PathOS project has completed 6 case studies that model Open Science pathways, measuring input indicators, costs, and outcomes. These case studies have tested and operationalised Open Science indicators, providing valuable data and expert insights from various local environments. They have also contributed to the Cost-Benefit Analysis and validated key results. Each case study tells a complete story, covering different objectives, implementation mechanisms, and actors across the research and innovation ecosystem.

Key Questions Explored in the PathOS Case Studies

Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence

Does Open Access increase the long-term influence, real-world uptake, and equity in climate-AI research?

Portuguese Repository Infrastructure RCAAP

How does Portugal's RCAAP infrastructure affect industry use, visibility, and reuse of research publications?

Effects of Data Repositories on Data Usage

How does repository type influence the reuse of research data, especially in the social sciences?

ELIXIR's Bioinformatics Resources

How do ELIXIR's open resources fuel innovation and industry-wide benefits?

Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications

Does the reusability of open COVID-19 artefacts influence downstream uptake in health and innovation?

French Open Access Infrastructure

How are French Open Science platforms used beyond academia, and by whom?

Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence

Examines how two distinct Open Access routes, self-archiving in repositories (Green Open Access) and journal-based publication with open licences (Published OA), differentially influence the thematic persistence and downstream uptake of AI and climate research in academic, industrial, and equity-related contexts.

DATA SOURCES USED

This case study uses publications and data from the OpenAIRE Knowledge Graph (for Open Access status, funding, and affiliations), Semantic Scholar (for citations), PATSTAT (for patent citations), and ROR.org (for organisation types). It focuses on AI and Climate Change publications across disciplines.

HIGH LEVEL METHODOLOGY

The methodology compares Open Access and closed-access publications using Propensity Score Matching (PSM) to isolate the causal effects of two specific Open Access routes: Green Open Access (repository-based self-archiving) and Published Open Access (journal-mediated with explicit open licences). Analyses draw on structured metadata from the OpenAIRE Graph API (for Open Access status and funding links), Semantic Scholar (for citation metrics), PATSTAT (for patent citations), and the SciNoBo platform (for field classification, citation impact, topic persistence, and Sustainable Development Goals relevance). Author gender is inferred from given names to examine gender equity. Economic and translational impact is assessed via patent links and science–industry collaboration patterns. A central focus is placed on whether different Open Access routes enhance the long-term persistence of AI-for-Climate research topics, with supporting attention to collaboration structures and gender participation.

CREATED DATA COLLECTION

Collection of AI and Climate Change publications, enriched with metadata such as research fields (FOS), citation impact (FWCI), author demographics, Open Access status, funding information, Sustainable Development Goals targets, and patent citations. This data identifies emerging and persistent topics in AI and Climate Change.

CREATED / UPDATED TOOLS

The case study led to the development of a tool for detecting persistent topics based on publication trends, citation impact, and topic longevity. Additional tools include an affiliation analysis tool for identifying organisation types and a publication-to-patent citation analysis tool to explore innovation links. Author gender classification was also applied to assess demographic patterns in research.

Academic Impact

Especially through Green Open Access routes, it significantly boosts citation impact and helps sustain the visibility of emerging AI and Climate Change research topics. Green Open Access is consistently associated with higher academic reach, stronger field-weighted impact, and markedly greater topic persistence over time. Published Open Access contributes to visibility but shows a weaker or even negative effect on long-term topic vitality.

- Citation impact
- Thematic persistence
- Diversity

Economic Impact

Green Open Access publications show stronger connections between research and industry, including higher science–industry collaboration rates and modest increases in patent citations. These findings suggest that repository-based access facilitates knowledge transfer and enhances the practical uptake of AI-for-Climate research.

- Science-industry collaboration (affiliation analysis, patent citations)

Societal Impact

Open Access articles, particularly those in the Published Open Access category, correlate with greater alignment to the Sustainable Development Goals and modest gains in gender equity, especially in increasing the share of women in senior (last-author) positions. However, Green Open Access is linked to a small decline in all-women author teams, highlighting the complex dynamics between openness and inclusion.

- Uptake in and impact on societal issues (SDG Targets)

Link to indicators from the [Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook](#)

The presented case study investigates whether the availability of Open Access publications in the Portuguese repository infrastructure, RCAAP, increases usage and collaborations between academia and industry.

DATA SOURCES USED

Data from OpenAIRE Knowledge Graph, ORBIS, and ROR.org is used to explore publications in the RCAAP (Open Access Repository of Portuguese Academic Publications). The focus is on metadata related to citation patterns, Open Access status, funding information, and the involvement of Portuguese companies in research.

HIGH LEVEL METHODOLOGY

The methodology for the RCAAP case study involves analysing citation impact and collaborations through A/B group comparisons and OA status. The study uses tools to assess citation impact and the level of cooperation in scientific research, with a focus on science-industry collaborations. The approach incorporates AI-driven, big data techniques to evaluate academic and economic impacts.

CREATED DATA COLLECTION

The collection of RCAAP and Portuguese publications is enriched with metadata on research fields (FOS), citation impact (FWCI), Open Access status, funding information, affiliation types, and Portuguese company affiliations.

CREATED / UPDATED TOOLS

The tools generate Affiliation Analysis (focusing on the type of organisation and its connection with Portuguese companies) and create Publication-Patent Citation Analysis, which together assess these publications' academic and economic impact.

Academic Impact

Identified that RCAAP Open Access publications have a strong citation impact and foster collaboration intensity, leading to improved visibility in academia.

- Citation impact
- Collaboration intensity

Economic Impact

Highlighted how RCAAP infrastructure contributes to cost savings and efficiency gains through mutualisation.

- Science-industry collaboration

Societal Impact

Not identified in this case study.

- Not applicable

Link to indicators from the Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook

The presented case study evaluates whether data hosted in a national platform leads to higher reuse or citation frequency than data shared through alternative repositories, illuminating how localised governance can shape OS adoption.

DATA SOURCES USED

Data from sources like OpenAlex, Scopus, and Data Citation Corpus are used to investigate data mentions in publications. The focus is on metadata related to datasets, their reuse, and citation patterns, particularly how research artefacts are created or reused, with a specific focus on the social sciences, and what role data repositories play.

HIGH LEVEL METHODOLOGY

The repository case study uses citation impact, dataset reuse, and field classifications to assess the academic impact of open data. The methodology involves citation impact analysis, field of science analysis, and artefact analysis to explore the reuse of research artefacts and their impact on academic communities.

CREATED DATA COLLECTION

Collection of SSH publications, enriched with metadata on research artefacts that were reused to study data mentions in SSH generally and the accuracy of algorithmic tools for extracting data mentions.

CREATED / UPDATED TOOLS

The tool adapts SciNoBo Research Artefact Analysis to create outputs that assess the academic impact of research artefacts and their reuse across various scientific disciplines.

Academic Impact

Demonstrated that the repository where data is shared is associated with citation and dataset reuse.

- Dataset reuse

Economic Impact

Not identified in this case study.

- Not applicable

Societal Impact

Not identified in this case study.

- Not applicable

[Link to indicators from the Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook](#)

The presented case study looks at how industry integrates Open Data and tools into their workflows, and whether usage analytics or patent references capture genuine economic and societal gains.

DATA SOURCES USED

Data for this case study is drawn from Semantic Scholar, EuropePMC, and PATSTAT, focusing on bioinformatics research. It includes metadata on publications, citation impact (FWCI), and reference counts. The study also looks at patents related to ELIXIR resources and digital skills in bioinformatics job vacancies.

HIGH LEVEL METHODOLOGY

This case study uses text mining techniques to extract publications and citation impact data, focusing on bioinformatics resources provided by ELIXIR. The methodology involves extracting patents and analysing economic growth, labour market impacts, and digital skills in the industry. Text mining for patent data, CBA (Cost-Benefit Analysis), including surveys and interviews to assess economic growth and cost savings for companies. The analysis of science-industry collaborations and patent citations is central to this study. AI-driven and big data techniques are employed to generate evidence of economic impact.

CREATED DATA COLLECTION

The collection of ELIXIR-supported publications is enriched with metadata such as research fields (FOS), citation impact (FWCI), and reference counts. Patents mentioning ELIXIR resources, and digital skills data from ELIXIR job vacancies.

CREATED / UPDATED TOOLS

The tools generate text mining techniques for extracting data from patents and create analysis on digital skills in the bioinformatics industry, enabling insights into the impact of ELIXIR resources on academic research and industry needs.

Academic Impact

Identified how using ELIXIR's public resources enhances citation impact and fosters interdisciplinary research.

- Citation impact
- Interdisciplinarity

Economic Impact

Highlighted the economic growth of companies through science-industry collaborations and how digital skills in bioinformatics lead to labour market benefits and cost savings

- Innovation output
- Economic growth of companies
- Labour market impacts
- Cost savings
- Science-industry collaborations

Societal Impact

Not identified in this case study.

- Not applicable

[Link to indicators from the Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook](#)

Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications

The presented case study investigates whether the referencing and reusing of datasets and software in COVID-19 research publications contributed to downstream impact, including mentions in patents and clinical trials or guidelines, highlighting how practical openness may support research translation during and beyond emergency-response contexts.

DATA SOURCES USED

This case study uses enriched data from OpenAIRE Knowledge Graph, Semantic Scholar, CORID-19 (full texts), PATSTAT, and ROR.org. It focuses on COVID-19-related publications and analyses citation impact, Open Access status, research affiliations, reuse of open artefacts such as datasets and software, and patent citations. The study also integrates data from PUBMED on citations in clinical trials and guidelines to assess uptake in medical practice.

HIGH LEVEL METHODOLOGY

This case study investigates the downstream effects of Open Science practices by analysing COVID-19 research publications that created datasets or software. Rather than comparing Open Access versus non-Open Access status, it focuses on two observable behaviours: referencing external research artefacts (traceability) and the documented reuse of shared artefacts by others (reusability). A regression-based analytical design with interaction terms estimates impact while controlling for scientific quality, citation exposure, publication year, author count, and artefact volume. Academic impact is assessed using tools that analyse citation impact, field of science classification, research community engagement, and the reuse of datasets and software. Economic impact is evaluated through analysis of affiliations by organisation type (academic or industry) and tracking of patent citations. Societal impact is measured by analysing how often publications are cited in clinical trials and guidelines. The methodology combines large-scale data analysis, AI techniques, and causal inference approaches to understand the effects of Open Science.

CREATED DATA COLLECTION

Collection of COVID-19 publications enriched with metadata on research fields (FOS), citation impact (FWCI), Open Access status, affiliation types, patent citations, created/reused research artefacts, and clinical trial and guideline citations.

CREATED / UPDATED TOOLS

The case study resulted in refinements and adaptations of the SciNoBo Citance Analysis and Research Artefact Analysis tools. New tools were developed for analysing affiliation types (academic, industry), tracking citations from patents, and examining research uptake through citations in clinical trials and medical guidelines.

Academic Impact

Demonstrated that the COVID-19 research community adopted Open Science practices at scale, including structured sharing and referencing datasets and software. Papers whose artefacts were reused showed modest gains in cross-sector collaboration and interdisciplinary visibility, especially when paired with high quality and early dissemination.

- Interdisciplinary and novelty
- Reproducibility: polarity of publications (engagement and stance of the community)

Economic Impact

Revealed that artefact reuse is positively associated with industry engagement and technological uptake. Publications with documented artefact reuse received more patent citations and showed stronger links to science-industry collaboration, highlighting their role in driving innovation.

- Science-industry collaboration (affiliation analysis, patent citations)

Societal Impact

Found that artefact reuse alone did not lead to increased clinical uptake. Once factors like study quality, visibility, and timing were accounted for, reused papers showed slightly fewer citations in clinical trials and guidelines, suggesting that clinical influence depends more on research credibility and timeliness than on reuse alone.

- Uptake in medical practice (citations in clinical trials and clinical guidelines)

Link to indicators from the Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook

The case study analyses how users within academia and other social and economic sectors access the publications in the two leading French Open Science portals (OpenEdition and HAL) and assesses whether Open Access publications are accessed more frequently than closed ones across different sectors, disciplines, and countries.

DATA SOURCES USED

This case study analyses connection logs from two major French Open Science platforms, OpenEdition and HAL, covering January 2023 to September 2024. We enrich the raw logs with OpenAlex metadata on publication topics and openness status. Using the IP addresses recorded in the logs and data from Ipinfo.io, we classify access to publications by national geolocation and according to Eurostat's Statistical Classification of Economic Activities.

HIGH LEVEL METHODOLOGY

The key question this case study addresses is whether making a resource openly available increases its likelihood of being accessed. Connection logs are collected, securely stored, indexed, and enriched with multiple classifications to enable aggregated analyses. The final dataset can be explored via an online web application that computes the open access advantage for any topic, sector, platform and geolocation combination.

CREATED DATA COLLECTION

Collection of non-academic connection logs from French Open Science resources, enriched with topic metadata, openness status, and sector engagement. This data helps understand how French Open Science resources are accessed and used outside academic circles.

CREATED / UPDATED TOOLS

The tools generate IP classification (based on Ipinfo, Elasticsearch and a custom Node.js script using llama3.3:latest) and adapt a middleware tool to enrich logs with openness status and scientific field of resources, providing deeper insights into the interactions between Open Science resources and non-academic users.

Academic Impact

Considering all disciplines and countries, Open Science publications have a distinctive 2.1% access advantage over closed publications.

- N/A

Economic Impact

For economic sectors other than education, the advantage of open science is more significant and amounts to 3.5%. Some sectors, like the Public administration and Professional activities, have even larger advantages, respectively 8% and 9%.

- Uptake by the economic sector

Societal Impact

Comparison between different countries reveals that an advantage for OS in many Global South and Global North countries: US (12%), India (9%), France (8%), China (8%), Canada (7%), Italy (7%), Portugal (7%), Singapore (6%), Bolivia (6%), Mozambique (6%).

- Open access advantage
- Uptake by the societal sector (topic, openness status, sector distribution)

[Link to indicators from the Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook](#)